

SINTEF

Top of caisson +3090

Highest Ast. Tide +2110

Mean High Water +1620

Mean Sea Level +1090

Mean Low Water +570

Sea bed level at caisson +370

Lowest Ast. Tide 0

Foundaion level -1110

Report

Design and production guide for ClimaRest timber caisson and soil anchor plate

Part of a sustainable solution for coastal protection for coastlines in cold regions

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SUMMARY

This report presents motivation, user requirements and design of timber caissons which as part of the CLIMAREST blueprint of blue-grey coastal protection at permafrost coastlines. The designed caisson is composed of two parts (upper and lower part) that allows exchange of the upper part should it be rotten. The lower part is permanently submerged under water. Possibility for easy replacement of the elements (should they be damaged or rotten) on the front seaside of caisson is also accounted for in the design. Caissons designed from timber members from the decommissioned Svea mines (Svalbard), such reuse of materials increases sustainability profile of the blueprint.

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Table of contents

1	Introduction	6
1.1	Motivation.....	6
2	Design premise for timber caisson.....	9
3	General design and main analysis.....	12
3.1	Stability calculations and selected environmental loads.....	12
3.1.1.1	Pressure from ice loads	12
3.1.1.2	Decking planks capacity.....	12
3.2	Structural strength of mooring line components.....	13
3.2.1	Mooring line hanger and adjustment device	13
3.2.1.1	Mooring bolt.....	13
3.2.1.2	Traveller Plate Design (CHAD)	13
3.2.1.3	Stud Bolt Design (CHAD).....	14
3.2.1.4	Hanger Plate Design (CHAD).....	15
3.2.1.5	Tension the mooring line.....	16
3.2.1.6	Hanger Yoke Design (CHAD)	16
3.2.1.7	Wired Hanger Design.....	17
3.2.1.8	Fastener Capacity from hanger yoke to bracings.....	18
3.2.1.9	Tension in Connecting Bolts Between Timber Caissons.....	18
3.2.1.10	Required diameter for washer	19
3.2.2	Calculation of Weights for Timber Caissons.....	20
3.2.2.1	Upper Caisson.....	20
3.2.2.2	Lower Caisson.....	20
3.2.2.3	Ballast Bag Dimensions.....	21
3.2.2.4	Axial_withdrawal capacity of bottom plank screws.....	21
4	Description and manufacturing guide for timber caisson	22
4.1	Brief.....	22
4.2	Components overview	23
4.2.1	Timber parts	25
4.2.2	Anchor load distribution yoke	26
4.2.2.1	Wire Hanger and Adjustment Design (WHAD).....	26
4.2.2.2	Chain Hanger and Adjustment Design (CHAD)	27
4.2.3	Timber fasteners.....	28
4.2.3.1	Countersunk flat head cladding screws.....	28
4.2.3.2	Flange head construction screw	28
4.2.3.3	A4 coach screw 10x130	28

4.2.4	Machine- and stud bolts	28
4.3	Workshop manufacturing description	29
5	Description and manufacturing guide for anchor plate	33
5.1	Brief	33
5.2	Components overview	34
5.2.1	Timber parts	34
5.2.2	Steel components	34
5.2.3	Timber fasteners	34
5.2.3.1	Flange head construction screw	34
5.2.3.2	Steel to timber details	35
5.3	Workshop manufacturing description	35
6	Installation	36
6.1	Brief	36
6.2	Components overview	36
6.2.1	Wire rope mooring line	36
6.2.2	Chained mooring line	37
6.3	Common preparations	37
6.4	Installation of anchor plate	37
6.5	Installation of lower caissons	37
6.5.1	Drained installation site	37
6.5.2	Tidal water in installation site	38
6.6	Installation of upper caissons	38
6.7	Connect and tensioning of mooring line	38
6.7.1	Wire rope mooring line	38
6.7.2	Chained mooring line	39
6.8	Completion	40
7	Acknowledgements	41
A	Fabrication drawing for ClimaRest Timber Caisson	42
B	Fabrication drawing for ClimaRest anchor plate	44
C	Generic stability calculations for timber caisson with environmental loads	46
D	Data sheet for Simpson Strong-Tie® Fastening System	57
D.1	Strong-Drive SDWS TIMBER SS Screw	57
D.2	Strong-Drive SDWH TIMBER-HEX SS Screw	61
D.3	A4 coach screw 10x130	65
8	References	68

APPENDICES

Klikk eller trykk her for å skrive inn tekst.

1 Introduction

Anatoly O. Sinitsyn

1.1 Motivation

This document presents the motivation, design, manufacturing guide, and installation guide of the ClimaRest timber caissons and anchor plate with mooring line. Timber caisson is a part of CLIMAREST prototype for coastal protection at permafrost coastlines. Drawings and calculations are found in the annex.

Wood was historically used as construction material for coastal infrastructure [1] and the idea of using timber caissons as revetments (revetments are onshore structures with the principal function of protecting the shoreline from erosion [2]) against coastal erosion is not new. Protective structures from timber against erosion on seacoasts or riverbanks were built as far as several hundreds of years back in Scandinavia, Northern America and Russia. For example, in Norway, the oldest riverbank protection is on Nidelva river in Trondheim was built in 1796, and it still functions. In the Arctic conditions, revetments made from timber (*ryazhi*) were probably also used for hundreds of years in the Russian north. Typical construction of timber revetment consists of a large box (several meters in height, width and depth), which is filled with rock or soil. Deployment may take place both in winter from the ice surface or in summer. The front part of the structure can be protected with rock rubble against scour and erosion.

Wood as a construction material is preferred from a sustainability aspect., Simple and affordable technologies when building infrastructure from timber may facilitate wider applicability of timber solutions for coastal and riverbank protection. Such a solution seems to be efficient for the remote locations as it requires transportation of relatively low amounts of timber and use of local soil for backfill. However, this needs to be supported by better technological solutions that will strengthen the advantages and eliminate the shortcomings when using timber in coastal and river engineering. This is also related to the conditions of cold regions, which are the focus areas for development of the CLIMAREST blueprint. We define the cold regions in terms of presence of at least one of the following factors: cold air temperatures; seasonal frost penetration; permafrost, including ground ice; seasonal or perennial sea-ice cover and/or ice cover in rivers, [3].

Advantages of using wood in coastal engineering consist of the following: wood is a renewable resource, it has high strength to weight ratio, it has high tolerance of impact from short duration loads, it has good resistance to abrasion; it provides ease of construction, on site repairs and recycling; wood has attractive appearance and natural durability; use of reused timber can be one the most favourable alternatives (among wood materials) [1]. The drawback consists in the following: variability in properties (as a signature of natural material), limited availability in large dimensions and high durability, species native to the cold climate have moderate durability (to marine environment and biological hazards), demonstration of sustainability is difficult as most species used in engineering applications have a long renewable time [1]. It is also important to remember that timber structures require maintenance and repair, which needs to be considered when planning investments. Marine structures from timber can be affected by the marine borers. However, this hazard is absent in cold Arctic waters, which have facilitated use of timber as a construction material for coastal infrastructure in the past. The situation may perhaps change in the future if the invasive species of marine borer will spread in a warmer Arctic.

An overview of durability and protection of timber structures in marine environments in Europe is presented in [4]. Environmentally friendly use of timber in harbour infrastructure in Norway is presented in [5]. Durability of wood and wood-based products is presented in standard [6], which specifies use class 5 (UC 5) as “a situation in which the wood or wood-based product is permanently or regularly submerged in salt water”. It is also specified that wood in marine environments can be subject to attack of marine invertebrate

organisms, fungi, and wood-boring insects. No preservatives are allowed to be used in the UC 5 [6]. Distribution of marine wood-borers of the Limnoriidae (hat causing large destruction to wooden structures exposed in the marine environment) in European coastal waters is reported by Borges *et al.* [7]. Diversity, environmental requirements, and biogeography of bivalve wood-borers (Teredinidae) in European coastal waters is reported by Borges *et al.* [8]. In Norway, marine borers were registered as far as in Tromsø [5, 9]. Up to date marine borers were not reported on Svalbard.

Analysis of performance of revetments built in form of timber caissons in Arctic conditions is limited. Lothe *et al.* [10] present evaluation of long-term (several decades) performance of caissons from three Russian settlements of Barentsburg, Pyramiden, and Coles Bay in Svalbard. Advantages according to evaluation of Lothe and Finseth [10] consist in the following: overall condition of caissons were found to be very good (caissons were found to be largely intact); they seemed to be strong enough to withstand ice forces; they are suitable for attachment of ice-protective skirt. The caissons that were used for erosion protection in Barentsburg has worked well. The following challenges were outlined: settlements (i.e. vertical displacements) due to leaching of material through the bottom and poor foundations; significant difficulties for reparation of separate members or failed foundations; in some cases – need in regular maintenance. In Svalbard, use of timber revetment was suggested by Finseth *et al.* [11] for protection of coastline and cultural heritage in Fredheim.

Figure 1. Timber caissons in Barentsburg (2011). Picture: Lothe, A./Finseth, J. © SINTEF AS.

In CLIMAREST project, the idea of using timber caisson for coastal protection emerge from two directions. We initially aimed to design coastal protection in form of submerged wave breakers. However, this direction was changed based on communication with the stakeholder, i.e. Port of Longyearbyen (Longyearbyen, Svalbard). Coastal erosion threatening several areas in Longyearbyen (Figure 2), including coastal stretch from the Tourist quay (*Turistkaia*) to the Old quay (*Gammelkaia*) (Figure 3). Director of Port of Longyearbyen, Kjetil Bråten had a vision of making a revetment from re-used wood from the decommissioned Svea mines. Hence, timber from Svea mines was delivered to Longyearbyen with the view to utilize it for coastal protection. Mr. Bråten has provided a visualization [12] of such revetment to the project. This visualization includes a wall from timber and a promenade. CLIMAREST used vision of Mr. Bråten as the departure point.

Areas affected by coastal erosion in Longyearbyen - potential for upscaling of CLIMAREST blueprint

Figure 2. Areas with coastal erosion in Longyearbyen -- potential for upscaling of CLIMAREST blueprint. Map: © TopoSvalbard, Norwegian Polar Institute.

Figure 3. Coastal stretch "Tourist quay -- the Old quay" in Longyearbyen and coastal profile on this stretch. Aerial picture: © TopoSvalbard, Norwegian Polar Institute.

CLIMAREST has envisioned that the developed prototype can be utilized in the future in design of coastal protection on the whole ca. 300-meter-long stretch “Tourist quay – the Old quay”, hence upscaling of developed solution can be achieved.

We also envisioned that this prototype will be applicable to other small settlements across the Arctic, in such case modifications of construction may be needed. This may concern (but not limited to) geometry of caissons that is defined by water depth by them and possible scour (as a function of wave climate), and dimensions of timber members that can be as a construction material (for CLIMAREST prototype we had no choice in selecting dimensions of the timber members as those were provided to us).

2 Design premise for timber caisson

Anatoly O. Sinitsyn

Design requirements are set up or developed based on recommendations in literature ([1]) and discussions with the stakeholder. Some of the requirements are tackling the disadvantages that are relevant when using timber for marine structures and the ones that are based on the observations from Svalbard ([10]).

The design premise consists in the following:

- General requirements – simple construction process for carpentry work to reduce chances of errors. This includes a minimal number of cuts and drilled holes.
- Caissons to be made from timber elements with the following dimensions: 2000 mm by 200 mm by 150 mm. these timber elements are not necessary ideally straight.
- Caisson composed in three sections; each section is approximately 2 m by 2 m in the plan (from the top) view. Dimensions in plan are dictated by dimensions of timber members that are available for this construction (Figure 4). Dimensions of caisson are approximately the following: 6000 mm (length along the seaside), 2000 mm (width in cross shore direction), 4200 mm (height). Dimensions may differ somewhat from the ones presented above should the design (e.g. the actual connection of timber elements) would require so..

Figure 4. Caisson consisting of two compartments.

- To overcome the issue of timber rot, the caisson should be composed of two parts (top and bottom). The lower part is submerged in water and hence it will not rot. The upper part is exposed to the air, and expected to be rotten in some 20-30 years, hence it needs to be easily replaceable. Detachable upper part will permit doing so. Each of these parts will be assembled in a workshop and will be delivered on the site as a whole. First, the bottom part to be installed (and filled the ground if needed), secondly the upper part to be installed on the top of it. A connection of those two parts needs to be designed. The exact heights of these parts may be affected by the fact that the anchors (2 pcs in total for the 4-m long caisson) would need to be connected 1250 mm below the top of the caisson.
- Data on loads (this data is presented in [13]):
 - Load from sea ice: 2 MPa.

Since the caisson has a 2-layer armour stone (inclined surface, that facilitates ice breaking due to flexural failure) for erosion protection it can be assumed that the global ice pressure on the caisson will be reduced to a lower value than 2 MPa. Lothe *et al.* [9] presents evaluation of long-term (several decades) performance of caissons from three Russian settlements of Barentsburg Pyramiden, and Coles Bay in Svalbard. According to Lothe and Finseth [9] caissons seemed to be strong enough to withstand ice forces.

- Load (including safety factors) in the anchor line is 185 kN. Hence, caisson needs to be anchored.
- Design requirements to timber friction plate for anchor:
 - Dimensions of anchor plate per one section of caisson: width $B=2.0$ m; height $t=0.5$ m; length $L=2.0$ m (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Principal sketch of soil anchor.

- Plate looks like a "grill". "Mesh" of the "grill" is made from "solid" walls, constructed from timber elements that are identical to the elements for the caisson (i.e. 2000 mm, by 200 mm, by 150 mm)
- Space between walls/beams will be filled with soil.
- The plate by itself, and the front wall of the plate need to be strong enough to accommodate attachment of two anchors, each of which has capacity of 185 kN. For this, a double front wall is suggested. It is a suggestion that may need to be evaluated.
- Anchor connections to the plate need to be designed
- Lifting operation for separate plates needs to be evaluated/designed, i.e. separate parts need to be strong enough to be lifted by a crane. Lifting points, additional arrangements (such as steel plates, etc., if any) for lifting operation need to be specified.
- Design of integration of anchor connections to the caisson. Standard anchor connections should be used (i.e. integrated) if possible. Anchors will be connected 1250 mm below the top of the caisson, three anchors per 6 m long caisson, each anchor is connected to the middle of 2 m long section/compartment. The capacity of each anchor is 185 kN. Calculations/assessment needs to be done that the anchor connection/the compartments are strong enough to accommodate load from the anchors.
- Design of connection of 2 m long caissons to each other to form a 6 m long timber caisson front towards the sea in total.
- Other design considerations:
 - Decking planks for pedestrians. The upper "lid" for the box needs to be adjustable to tailor the upper surface to differential settlements of neighbouring caissons.
 - Replaceable seaside cladding (to replace rotten elements of the caisson in the future).

- Use the timber members from Svea: with as less adapting and machining as possible (to save time and effort).
- Easy buildable using simple tools and with off-the-shelf fasteners.
- The parts of the caisson shall be handled by front loader or other commonly available lifting machinery.
- The anchor load activates in two steps: in the first step the anchor resistance is activated by backfilling the soil behind the caisson; in the second step the anchor load will be increased by forced tension.
- To withstand load from the backfill, and external actions as ice and wave loads.
- Lifting operation for installation of timber caisson (lower and upper parts) needs to be designed:
 - Strength of parts during lifting operation needs to be checked.
 - Necessary arrangements/attached steel details (if any) for the lifting operation.
 - Attachment points for the straps need to be specified.
 - Weight of each part (i.e. bottom and upper part) needs to be defined.
 - Bottom of the caisson:
 - Spacings between timber member should assure that there will be no issues for filling the caisson with water during the deployment.
 - Bolts/connection elements:
 - Acid-proof elements suitable for the use in sea water
 - Specification for the bolts/connection elements (dimensions, number)
- Bags with soil will be placed inside of the caissons after they are installed. Soil from the excavation for the caissons will be used to fill up the bags. Placing bags filled with soil (instead of placing soil directly in the caissons) should assure replacement of the members on the front part of caisson (so that soil will not leak out if the front members are detached) and replacement of the upper part. The lifetime of the material for the bags shall be at least 25 years. Two options for material of the bags are considered – impermeable material in case of local soil is polluted or non-woven material. Two sizes for bags may be considered:
 - a. One or two big geotextile (2.1 by 2.1 by 2.5 m or 2.1x2.1x ca. 4 m) bags placed inside and then filled up. Two caissons – two or four bags in total. Bags need to be closed after being filled up with soil. This is done either by sewing the bags or tightening the upper part with a rope.
 - b. Ca. 30 smaller bags (per caisson, i.e. 60 bags in total). Those bags are filled in first, then lifted and placed inside. Some additional arrangements (as large funnel) may be needed for filling up the bags. They are strong enough to be lifted, they will be ca. 700-750 kg each.

Option “a.” seems to be the most convenient.

We also think that the timber caisson should have an advantage compared to some other solutions, such as the ones that are relying on piles. It is usual that the piles need to be installed with high precision which is difficult to achieve in practice. For example, the vision presented in [12] (a revetment made from timber) may rely on H-piles installed with a high accuracy.

3 General design and main analysis

Sveinung Ørjan Nesheim

3.1 Stability calculations and selected environmental loads

Calculation of stability and capacity of beams and girders has been performed and is included in Annex C. Some additional calculations are provided below. As seen from the calculations, the suction load from waves and ice leads was too high in the first design. Therefore, the Ice Load Reinforcement Frame (ILoRF) was introduced to distribute loads to the opposite side of the timber caisson. This is a significant advantage because the ice load is transferred to the soil, and the cladding subject to suction load from waves may be fastened with more fasteners anchored in the wood normal to the grain. However, ice conditions are milder than supposed in calculations, and there have been no reports of timber caissons crushed by ice loads to our knowledge. Calculations are according to Eurocode 5.

3.1.1.1 Pressure from ice loads

Bending strength

$k_{mod}=1$ and $\gamma_m=1.15$

$L_{member}=\text{hangerSpan}$

$L_{member}=0.6$

$f_m=24$ [MPa]

$f_{m,d}=f_m*k_{mod}/\gamma_m$

Allowed shear stress:

$f_v=4$ [MPa]

$p_{ice}=2e6$ [Pa]

$q_{ice}=p_{ice}*h_{member}$

$M_{ice}=q_{ice}*L_{member}^2/8$

$V_{ice}=q_{ice}*L_{member}/2$

$S_{member_hk}=(t_{member}*h_{member}^2)/6$

$S_{member_flask}=(h_{member}*t_{member}^2)/6$

$bendingStress_{ice}=M_{ice}/S_{member_flask}/1e6$ [N/mm²]

$n_{bend_ice}=100/f_m*bendingStress_{ice}$

Capacity bending from ice: 100 %

3.1.1.2 Decking planks capacity

$k_{mod}=0.65$ (Short term service class 3) and $\gamma_m=1.3$

$L_{deck}=TC_width$

$f_m=24$ [MPa]

$f_{m,d}=f_m*k_{mod}/\gamma_m$

$p_{walk}=2e6$ [Pa]

$S_{deck_flat}=(h_{member}*(t_{member}/2)^2)/6$

$bendCapDeck=f_{m,d}*S_{deck_flat}*1e6$

Evenly distributed load

$w_{deckPerPlank}=8*bendCapDeck/L_{deck}^2$

$w_{deckArea}=w_{deckPerPlank}/h_{member}/1000$

Capacity UDL deck planks [kN/m²]: 22

3.2 Structural strength of mooring line components

3.2.1 Mooring line hanger and adjustment device

This is the calculation of the mooring line hanger and adjustment device that distributes the load from the mooring line into the Timber caissons. There are also additional calculations for various structural parts of the timber caisson. The calculations are mostly performed sequentially following the load path from the mooring line to the timber caisson.

3.2.1.1 Mooring bolt

When a CHAD is used, or where the mooring load is transferred by a single mooring bolt. The mooring bolt is designed to be a grade 8.8, and the following calculation gives the minimum diameter of the bolt.

$$\tau_{\text{allow}} = \frac{\sigma_{\text{tensile}}}{\gamma_{\text{shear}}} \times 0.6$$

$$d_{\text{min}} = \sqrt{\frac{4F_{\text{mooring}}}{\pi\tau_{\text{allow}}}}$$

Using the given parameters:

- $F_{\text{mooring}} = 185000 \text{ N}$
- $\sigma_{\text{tensile}} = 830 \times 10^6 \text{ Pa}$
- $\gamma_{\text{shear}} = 1.5$

The proposed mooring bolt diameter is M27, with a required hole diameter of 1.1 times the bolt diameter.

3.2.1.2 Traveller Plate Design (CHAD)

From the mooring bolt the load is transferred to a traveller. This traveller is made of two S355 plates, one on top and one below the mooring chain. The capacity of the traveller is bending moment driven. The bending moment is caused by the span between the mooring bolt and the stud bolts that the traveller is following. In the following calculations gives the minimum width of the plates of the traveller.

Given Parameters:

- Centre distance between stud bolts: $CC_{\text{studBolts}} = 0.25 \text{ m}$
- Maximum bending moment of traveller plate:

$$M_{\text{max, traveller}} = \frac{F_{\text{mooring}}}{2} \cdot \frac{CC_{\text{studBolts}}}{4}$$

(Since the traveller consists of two parallel plates, F_{mooring} is halved.)

- Proposed plate thicknesses for traveller plate: $t_{\text{traveller}} = [10, 12, 16, 20] \text{ mm}$
- Ultimate stress: $\sigma_{\text{ultimate}} = 355 \times 10^6 \text{ Pa}$
- Safety factor for traveller plate: $\gamma_{\text{traveller}} = 1$

Section Modulus and Required Plate Width

The required minimum section modulus is:

$$W_{\min, \text{traveller}} = \frac{M_{\max, \text{traveller}}}{\sigma_{\text{ultimate}}/\gamma_{\text{traveller}}}$$

The required plate width is:

$$w_{\text{traveller}} = \sqrt{\frac{6W_{\min, \text{traveller}}}{t_{\text{traveller}}}} \times 1000$$

The final design values of traveller plate are presented in the below table, showing thickness vs. required width.

Thickness [mm]	width [mm]
10.0	120.2
12.0	109.7
15.0	98.2
20.0	85.0

In the following 15 mm plate is used.

3.2.1.3 Stud Bolt Design (CHAD)

The traveller transfer the mooring load to two stud bolts. The function of the stud bolts is to adjust the tension of the mooring line. The design calculation assume that the load is taken on one of the bolts during tensioning (calculated in safety factor). The load on each stud bolt is determined assuming an unbalanced tensioning factor of $\gamma=2.5$. The required minimum diameter is:

$$\sigma_{\text{allow}} = \frac{\sigma_{\text{tensile}}}{\gamma_{\text{tensile}}}$$

$$d_{\min} = \sqrt{\frac{4F_{\text{mooring}}/2}{\pi\sigma_{\text{allow}}}}$$

The selected stud bolt diameter is M20.

3.2.1.4 Hanger Plate Design (CHAD)

The load in the stud bolts is transferred to a hanger plate. The function of the hanger plate is both to anchor the stud bolts, and to off-load the traveller if the traveller is required connect to a new link further up the mooring line.

Given Parameters and moments

- Proposed plate thicknesses: $t_{\text{plate}} = [16, 20, 32, 40]$ mm
- Hanger plate span: $L_{\text{hangerPl}} = CC_{\text{studBolts}} - \frac{OD_{\text{travellerHub}}}{1000}$
- Maximum bending moment (encastred plate):

$$M_{\text{max, hangerPl}} = \frac{F_{\text{mooring}} \cdot L_{\text{hangerPl}}}{8}$$

- Angle between hanger yoke and plate: $\theta_{\text{hangerPl}} = 45^\circ$
- Effective moment considering angle:

$$M_{\text{max,eff}} = \cos(\theta_{\text{hangerPl}}) \cdot M_{\text{max, hangerPl}}$$

- Tilt angle wrt. horizontal plane: $\theta_{\text{tilt}} = 30^\circ$
- Moment components:

$$M_{\text{max, hangPlInPlane}} = \cos(\theta_{\text{hangerPl}}) \cdot M_{\text{max,eff}}$$

$$M_{\text{max, hangPlPerp}} = \sin(\theta_{\text{hangerPl}}) \cdot M_{\text{max,eff}}$$

- Safety factor for hanger plate: $\gamma_{\text{hangerPl}} = 1$

Section modulus and plate width requirements

In-Plane control:

The required section modulus for in-plane bending:

$$W_{\text{min, hangPlInPlane}} = \frac{M_{\text{max, hangPlInPlane}}}{\sigma_{\text{ultimate}} / \gamma_{\text{hangerPl}}}$$

Required plate width for in-plane bending:

$$L_{\text{hangerPl, InPlane}} = \sqrt{\frac{6W_{\text{min, hangPlInPlane}}}{t_{\text{plate}}}} \times 1000$$

Out-of-plane control

The required section modulus for out-of-plane bending:

$$W_{\text{min, hangPlPerp}} = \frac{M_{\text{max, hangPlPerp}}}{\sigma_{\text{ultimate}} / \gamma_{\text{hangerPl}}}$$

Required plate width for out-of-plane bending:

$$L_{\text{hangerPl, Perp}} = \frac{6W_{\text{min, hangPlInPlane}}}{t_{\text{plate}}^2} \times 1000$$

Hanger plate dimensions

The required minimum plate dimensions for different proposed thicknesses are presented in the final table.

Variations	0	1	2	3
Thickness	15.0	20.0	30.0	40.0
L_inPlane	63.6	55.1	45.0	39.0
L_perp	269.8	151.8	67.4	37.9

Here a 15 mm plate with a doubling to 30 mm is used for the design.

3.2.1.5 Tension the mooring line

There is a relation between the tension produces by the stud bolts and the torsional nut moment. An estimated tension of the chain can be found by the following simple expressions:

Desired tension force in Newtons: $F_{\text{perStud}} = F_{\text{mooring}}/2$

Torque coefficient (assumed for lubricated stainless steel): $K1 = 0.12$

Torque coefficient (lubricated rigging screw): $K2 = 0.15$

Calculate required torque in Newton-meters for stud bolts [Nm]: $T1 = K1 * d_{\text{studBolt}} * F_{\text{perStud}}$

Calculate required torque in Newton-meters for 2" rigging screw [Nm]: $T2 = K2 * 25.4 * 2 * F_{\text{perStud}}$

The required torque is **220 Nm** for M20 stainless

The required torque is **700 Nm** for 2" rigging screw

3.2.1.6 Hanger Yoke Design (CHAD)

The load in the stud bolts is transferred to a hanger plate. The function of the hanger plate is both to anchor the stud bolts, and to off-load the traveller if the traveller is required connect to a new link further up the mooring line. The hanger plate is both tilted and designed with an angle towards anchor of the mooring line, hence the in-plane and out-of-plane control:

Given Parameters

- **Hanger span:** $L_{\text{hanger}} = 1.36 \text{ m}$
- **Available tube outer diameters (OD):** Extracted from available dimensions

Required Wall Thickness Calculation

$$\sigma_{\text{allowable}} = \frac{\sigma_{\text{ultimate}}}{\gamma_{\text{yoke}}}$$

The **maximum bending moment** is calculated for a **simple beam with two point loads equally spaced**, where a is the length from brace to point of loading.

$$M_{\text{max}} = \frac{F_{\text{mooring}}}{2} \cdot a$$

The required **minimum second moment of area** is:

$$I_{\text{min}} = \frac{M_{\text{max}} \cdot R_o}{\sigma_{\text{allowable}}}$$

The **required inner diameter** is calculated as:

$$R_i = \left(R_o^4 - \frac{4I_{min}}{\pi} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}}$$

$$D_i = 2R_i$$

Thus, the required **minimum wall thickness** is:

$$t_{required} = R_o - R_i$$

Matching Available Tube Dimensions

To ensure compatibility with available tube dimensions, the selected tube must meet:

$$T_{available} \geq t_{required}$$

The best-matching tubes are identified based on the available options.

Final Tube Selection

The possible designs for hanger yoke tubes (S355 material) are listed in the final table, showing outer diameter (OD) and required minimum thickness (Tmin).

OD	[mm]	T [mm]
0	150.0	20.0
1	160.0	12.5
2	168.3	10.0
3	170.0	12.5
4	180.0	12.5
5	190.0	12.5
6	193.7	8.0

Calculations show that Ø193.7 x 8 mm consume less material, but the larger diameter cause other parts to consume more material, and the option Ø168.3 x 10.0 is chosen. The higher material thickness also better fit with the dimension of the weld and the stress concentrations caused by the welding.

3.2.1.7 Wired Hanger Design

Alternative design for wired mooring line (WHAD)

Given Parameters

- ILoRF width is the span for the yoke: $W_{ILoRF} = 0.45$ m
- Two tubes are used (OD x t): Ø168 x 8 and Ø150 x 10

$\gamma_{hangerWHAD} = 1.5$

$$W_{min_WHAD} = \frac{\frac{F_{mooring} * W_{ILoRF}}{4}}{\frac{\sigma_{ultimate}}{\gamma_{WHAD}}}$$

$$V_{WHAD, 1} = \frac{\pi}{32} \frac{(0.1683^4 - (0.1683 - 0.008)^4)}{0.1683}$$

$$V_{WHAD, 2} = \frac{\pi}{32} \frac{(0.15^4 - (0.15 - 0.01)^4)}{0.15}$$

Final capacity 80% with 1.5 safety factor

3.2.1.8 Fastener Capacity from hanger yoke to bracings

The hanger yoke is transferring the mooring load to 4 timber braces in the timber caissons. The required capacity of the fasteners is calculated in the following:

Given Parameters

- **Load imposed per bracing:**

$$F_{\text{brace}} = \frac{F_{\text{mooring}}}{4}$$

- **Fastener diameter:** $d_{\text{fastener}} = 10 \text{ mm}$

- **Fastener length:** $l_{\text{fastener}} = 0.1 \text{ m}$

- **Characteristic embedment strength in wood:** $F_h = 24 \times 10^6 \text{ Pa}$

- **Material safety factor:** $\gamma_M = 1.5$

- **Fastener moment capacity:**

$$M_{y,Rk} = \frac{180}{600} \times \sigma_{\text{bolt}} \times d_{\text{fastener}}^{2.6}$$

Shear Strength of Fasteners

For a **thin steel plate** ($t \leq 0.5d$) in single shear:

- **Type A:**

$$F_{v,Rk,0} = 0.4 \times F_h \times d_{\text{fastener}} \times l_{\text{fastener}}$$

- **Type B (except withdrawal capacity):**

$$F_{v,Rk,1} = 1.15 \times \sqrt{2 \times M_{y,Rk} \times F_h \times d_{\text{fastener}}}$$

The **characteristic shear capacity** of the fastener is:

$$F_{v,Rk} = \min(F_{v,Rk,0}, F_{v,Rk,1})$$

The **design shear capacity** is:

$$F_{v,Rd} = \frac{F_{v,Rk}}{\gamma_M}$$

Number of Fasteners Required

The required number of fasteners per bracing is:

$$n_{\text{fastener}} = \left\lceil \frac{F_{\text{brace}}}{F_{v,Rd}} \right\rceil$$

Thus, the required number of $\emptyset 10 \text{ mm}$ screws per bracing is $n_{\text{fastener}} = 8 \text{ ea.}$

Proposed fastener type: $\emptyset 10 \times 120 \text{ mm}$ 304 Hex Coach Screw

3.2.1.9 Tension in Connecting Bolts Between Timber Caissons

Geometric analysis for tension on connecting bolts between timber caissons as following:

Given Parameters

- Timber caisson width: $W_{TC} = 2.0$ m
- Timber caisson depth: $D_{TC} = 2.3$ m
- Splitting moment due to mooring force:

$$M_{\text{splitting}} = \frac{F_{\text{mooring}}}{2} \cdot W_{TC}$$

- Connecting force required:

$$F_{\text{connect}} = \frac{M_{\text{splitting}}}{TC_{\text{depth}}}$$

- Number of connectors: $n_{TC\text{connectors}} = 2$

- Force per connector:

$$F_{\text{connector}} = \frac{F_{\text{connect}}}{n_{TC\text{connectors}}}$$

- Safety factor for unbalanced tensioning: $\gamma_{\text{tensileLoad}} = 2.5$

Required Bolt Diameter Calculation

The allowable tensile stress is:

$$\sigma_{\text{allow}} = \frac{\sigma_{\text{bolt}}}{\gamma_{\text{tensileLoad}}}$$

The minimum required bolt diameter is:

$$d_{\text{min}} = \sqrt{\frac{4 \cdot \frac{F_{\text{connector}}}{2}}{\pi \cdot \sigma_{\text{allow}}}}$$

The calculated minimum bolt diameter is M16, but M20 is proposed to reduce the number of design variations.

3.2.1.10 Required diameter for washer

Here a calculation for the required external diameter for a steel sleeve resting on timber parallel to the grain is shown, ensuring the bearing stress does not exceed the timber capacity.

Given Parameters

- Internal diameter timber bearing area: $d_{\text{inner}} = 0.025$ m
- Bearing capacity of timber (perpendicular to fiber): $\sigma_{\text{timber}} = 5 \times 10^6$ Pa

Required External Diameter Calculation

The required bearing area is calculated as:

$$A_{\text{required}} = \frac{F_{\text{connector}}}{\sigma_{\text{timber}}}$$

Solving for the external diameter:

$$d_{\text{outer}} = \sqrt{\frac{4A_{\text{required}}}{\pi} + d_{\text{inner}}^2}$$

Required washer diameter

The calculated required external diameter for the washer is: 76 mm or 68 mm square washer.

3.2.2 Calculation of Weights for Timber Caissons

3.2.2.1 Upper Caisson

Timber Properties

Timber density: $\rho_{\text{timber}} = 550 \text{ kg/m}^3$

Member cross-section: $A_{\text{member}} = 0.2 \times 0.15 \text{ m}^2$

Member length: $L_{\text{member}} = 2 \text{ m}$

Running meters of timber: $\text{runningMeters}_{UC} = 2 \times (11 \times 4 - 1 + \frac{11}{2} + 6 \times 2) + 4 \times 0.3 + 7 \times 2$

Timber volume: $V_{\text{membersUC}} = \text{runningMeters}_{UC} \times A_{\text{member}}$

Timber mass: $m_{\text{membersUC}} = V_{\text{membersUC}} \times \rho_{\text{timber}}$

Steel Components

Steel density: $\rho_{\text{steel}} = 7850 \text{ kg/m}^3$

Volume of CHAD plate: $V_{\text{CHAD, plate}} = 0.015 \times 2 \times (0.6 \times 0.25 + 0.4 \times 0.15 + 0.08 \times 0.35 + 0.4 \times 0.1)$

Volume of CHAD tube: $V_{\text{CHAD, tube}} = \frac{\pi}{4} (0.1683^2 - (0.1683 - 2 \times 0.008)^2) \times \text{hangerSpan}$

Buoyancy & Mass Calculations

Seawater density: $\rho_{\text{seawater}} = 1025 \text{ kg/m}^3$

Buoyancy of upper caisson: $\text{buoyancy}_{UC} = (V_{\text{CHAD, tube}} + V_{\text{CHAD, plate}} + V_{\text{membersUC}}) \times \rho_{\text{seawater}} = 4200 \text{ kg}$ (completely submerged)

Steel mass: $m_{\text{CHAD}} = (V_{\text{CHAD, tube}} + V_{\text{CHAD, plate}}) \times \rho_{\text{steel}}$

Fasteners

Fastener mass per unit: $m_{\text{fastener}} = (\frac{\pi}{4} \times 0.01^2 \times 0.25) \times \rho_{\text{steel}}$

Number of fasteners: $n_{\text{fastenersUC}} = \frac{\text{runningMeters}_{UC}}{2} \times 4$

Total fastener mass: $m_{\text{fastenersUC}} = m_{\text{fastener}} \times n_{\text{fastenersUC}}$

Total upper caisson mass: $m_{UC} = m_{\text{CHAD}} + m_{\text{membersUC}} + m_{\text{fastenersUC}} = 2400 \text{ kg}$

Required effective (submerged) ballast bag mass for upper caisson: $m_{\text{requiredBagUC}} = \text{buoyancy}_{UC} - m_{UC} = 1805 \text{ kg}$

3.2.2.2 Lower Caisson

Running meters: $\text{runningMeters}_{LC} = 2 \times (8 \times 4 + 9 + 4) + 4 \times 1.67 + 4 \times 2 + 2 \times 4$

Timber volume: $V_{\text{membersLC}} = \text{runningMeters}_{LC} \times A_{\text{member}}$

Buoyancy of lower caisson: $\text{buoyancy}_{LC} = V_{\text{membersLC}} \times \rho_{\text{seawater}} = 3465 \text{ kg}$

Timber mass: $m_{\text{membersLC}} = V_{\text{membersLC}} \times \rho_{\text{timber}}$

Number of fasteners: $n_{\text{fastenersLC}} = \frac{\text{runningMeters}_{LC}}{2} \times 4$

Fastener mass: $m_{\text{fastenersLC}} = m_{\text{fastener}} \times n_{\text{fastenersLC}}$

Total lower caisson mass: $m_{LC} = m_{\text{membersLC}} + m_{\text{fastenersLC}} = 1895 \text{ kg}$

Required effective (submerged) ballast bag mass for lower caisson: $m_{\text{requiredBagLC}} = \text{buoyancy}_{LC} - m_{LC} = 1575 \text{ kg}$

3.2.2.3 Ballast Bag Dimensions

Gravel density: $\rho_{\text{gravel}} = 2000 \text{ kg/m}^3$

Submerged gravel density: $\rho_{\text{gravel}} - \rho_{\text{seawater}}$

Bag area: $A_{\text{bag}} = \text{hangerSpan} \times L_{\text{member}}$

Minimum bag height for lower caisson: $\text{minH}_{\text{bag, LC}} = \frac{m_{\text{requiredBagLC}}}{A_{\text{bag}} \times \rho_{\text{gravelSubmerged}}} = 590 \text{ mm}$ **Note: This height is manually set to 600 mm to have proper downward force**

Minimum bag height for upper caisson: $\text{minH}_{\text{bag, UC}} = \frac{m_{\text{requiredBagUC}}}{A_{\text{bag}} \times \rho_{\text{gravelSubmerged}}} = 680 \text{ mm}$

Weight of gravel bag for lower caisson in air (at 550 mm): $A_{\text{bag}} * \text{minH}_{\text{bag, LC}} * \rho_{\text{gravel}} = 3265 \text{ kg}$

Weight of gravel bag for upper caisson in air: $A_{\text{bag}} * \text{minH}_{\text{bag, UC}} * \rho_{\text{gravel}} = 3700 \text{ kg}$

Total lifted mass in air of lower caisson with dead weight: $m_{\text{airLift LC wBag}} = m_{\text{LC}} + m_{\text{bagLCinAir}} = 5200 \text{ kg}$

3.2.2.4 Axial withdrawal capacity of bottom plank screws

Characteristic withdrawal strength: $f_{\text{ax,k}} = 0.015 \times \rho_{\text{timber}}$

Design axial withdrawal capacity: $F_{\text{ax,k}} = \frac{f_{\text{ax,k}} \times d \times l_e f}{\gamma_M}$

$n_{\text{fastenersUC}} = \frac{\text{runningMeters}_{\text{UC}}}{2} \times 4$

Number of fasteners bottom planks to counteract buoyancy including 1.5 in load factor:

$n_{\text{fastenersBottom}} = \frac{(\text{buoyancy}_{\text{UC}} + \text{buoyancy}_{\text{LC}}) \times 1.5 \times 9.81}{F_{\text{ax,k}}}$

Required number of fasteners to counteract buoyance: 22 ea.

4 Description and manufacturing guide for timber caisson

Sveinung Ørjan Nesheim

4.1 Brief

The timber caisson is designed to be made of members from the Svea mine with as less adapting and machining as possible. The main parts of the timber caisson will be assembled in a workshop. These parts are designed to be transported on a normal tipper truck (norsk: grusbil). The timber caisson is designed to allow manufacturing with simple tools and off-the-shelf fasteners. Furthermore, the components and finalized parts of the caisson shall be handled by front loader or other commonly available lifting machinery. The anchoring load should activate as much of the caisson as reasonably practicable. The maximum lifting weight for any part without optional dead weight is 2400 kg.

The timber caisson must withstand soil pressure to balance the capacity of the anchor load, and the anchor point load must be distributed to the structural parts of the timber caisson. Load from internal masses must also be handled. The pressure from ice load and suction force from wave slamming has proved to be the dimensioning design actions.

Seaside cladding members is designed to be replaceable. The caissons are also designed so that these can be arranged with some flexibility along the shore. Together with the capacity of the anchor plate, each timber caisson has structural integrity on its own.

The timber caisson is composed of three main timber parts: The lower and the upper part of the timber caisson and the central ice load reinforcement frame. These parts will be assembled in a workshop and delivered to the installation site as two parts (upper and lower timber caisson, and with the ice load reinforcement frame integrated in these two parts). The fourth main part is made from stainless steel and is the anchor load distribution yoke. This steel part will be delivered prefabricated from the mainland and installed in the upper part of the timber caisson.

The installation on site will be done sequentially. Given that the installation site is drained, the lower part of the timber caisson will be installed without the internal dead weight. The lifting weight is then 1900 kg. If, however, the installation site is not drained, the lower caisson must be installed with a minimum dead weight to ensure that the lower part does not float. The combined dry weight is then 5200 kg. If several timber caissons are to be installed in the same operation, it is recommended that all the lower parts are installed and levelled first. There are designated assembly screws used to align adjacent lower caissons.

Secondly the upper part will be installed on the top of the lower part. The lower and upper part are tied together with threaded rods. The lower and upper part does not have equal height. The lower part is designed to be in practice constantly submerged, and therefore in conditions that preserve the timber.

The timber caisson will be anchored to a friction plate (also referred to as an anchor plate) that is buried in the soil. The anchor line (or mooring line as it is also referred to), will be connected 1250 mm below the top of the caisson. There will be one friction plate per timber caisson. The capacity of each anchor is 185 kN, and the capacity of the timber caissons and the anchor load distribution yoke is designed based on this action.

4.2 Components overview

In the following five figures the timber caisson assembly is presented. All figures are shown with the seaside towards right. Figure 6 and Figure 7 shows the top view of the timber caisson assembly with preferably wire or optional chain as anchor line.

In Figure 8 a side view of the upper caisson is shown. The side view is showing the hanger yoke with wire as mooring line (section E-E). The Chain Hanger and Adjustment Device (CHAD) from early design of the timber caisson is here replaced with a slim yoke with four pad eyes for 801 Gunnebo turnbuckles, wire grab frogs and shackles. Figure 9 is showing the lower caisson. Due to the position of the side view, the ice load reinforcement frame is not shown in Figure 8 nor Figure 9.

The ice load reinforcement frame (ILoRF) is shown in Figure 10. Parts 6 and 7 of the ILoRF is integrated in the upper part of the timber caisson, whilst parts 8 are integrated in the lower part of the timber caisson.

Figure 6: Top view of timber caisson assembly with wired anchor line

Figure 7: Optional mooring: Top view of timber caisson assembly with chained anchor line.

Figure 8: Side view Upper Caisson: section E-E (A-A)

Figure 9: Side view Lower Caisson: section B-B

Figure 10: Side and top projection of Ice Load Reinforcement Frame (ILoRF)

4.2.1 Timber parts

Timber caisson (TC): Complete timber structure with anchor load distribution yoke. The timber caisson consists of one upper caisson and one lower caisson.

Lower caisson (LC): Bottom part of the timber caisson. This part is first lifted in place and makes the foundation for the upper caisson.

Upper caisson (UC): This part is lifted on top of the lower caisson first with only two decking planks mounted. The rest of the decking planks are mounted on site.

Member: Structural body that comes from the Svea mine timber planks.

Cladding (0): Members mounted as the exterior vertical skirt/cladding of the timber caissons.

Bottom planks (0): Members mounted on the bottom of the lower caisson.

Decking: Decking is made of deck planks mounted on top of the upper caisson and forms structure of the timber caisson that can be used for pavement.

Deck planks (1): Members split longitudinally to form 200 x 75 mm planks.

Columns (2): Vertical members for fastening cladding and braces, and for cladding/brace load distribution.

Tie bar (3): Members added to the column that ties the column members of the LC and UC together.

Braces (4): Diagonal members for lateral stiffness of the timber caisson in the plane perpendicular to the shoreline. The upper caisson has two levels of bracings: the top (4T) and middle (4M) bracing. The lower caisson the bottom (4B) bracing. Load in braces are designed to be transferred both to the cladding and to the columns. The braces help distribute the load to the columns and the entire cladding surfaces, and finally to and from soil and sea loads.

Bottom withdrawal reinforcement (5): two parallel members placed inside of the lower caisson on the bottom to reinforce fastening of bottom planks. The bottom withdrawal reinforcement members are structurally integrated with the lower part of the ILoRF.

Central ice load reinforcement frame (6): Two withstand the 2MPa iceload and the wave slamming suction force, and internal reinforcement frame is introduced. The mooring line will run between the twin vertical members of the reinforcement frame.

Upwards (optional) extension of (seaside) reinforcement (7): High tide in combination with wave slamming may require reinforcement in the upper part. The internal ice load reinforcement frame (6) is designed to accommodate centric vertical members that is anchored between the parallel vertical members of (6), and extended upwards with a free end, only fasted to the seaside cladding planks. The upwards extension can also be mounted on both seaside and opposite side of the timber caisson to allow for intermediate supports of the cladding planks. This can be mounted if the capacity of the decking should handle more load than pedestrians.

Downwards extension of reinforcement (8): As the ice load is concentrated below the water line, an extension of the internal reinforcement frame should be mounted. The internal ice load reinforcement frame (6) is designed to accommodate a centric vertical member that is anchored between the parallel vertical members of (6), and extended downwards and anchored between the bottom withdrawal reinforcement members. To better distribute this load, a vertical member is also mounted on the opposite side, extending from between (5) to between vertical members of (6).

Skid preventer (9): Four members installed underneath the lower caisson to increase seabed friction.

4.2.2 Anchor load distribution yoke

A yoke is designed to distribute the load from the anchor line to the timber caisson, and that allows the tension of the mooring line to be adjusted. Due to the high ice load pressure, the yoke is also designed to transfer ice load pressure to the soil. There are two alternative designs:

4.2.2.1 Wire Hanger and Adjustment Design (WHAD)

Simplified hanger yoke with four pad eyes in addition to a centric reinforced tube where the wire will be hanged in a loop. The central piece is the main position for hanging off the wire, whilst the four pad eyes are on this early version of the WHAD placed there for safety and additional anchor points for shackles. The adjustment of the tension in the wire will be done with turnbuckles first in combination with frog legs/wire rope clamps and finally to a more permanent open wedge socket with bolt between the turnbuckle and a wire loop around the WHAD.

The advantage of this latest version of the WHAD is that it has two plates placed 1/3 from the ends of the yoke that transfer not only load from the anchor line to the timber caisson, but also distribute ice and sea loads to the opposite side of the timber caisson through the ILoRF. This is a huge advantage because ice load is transferred to the soil, and the cladding subject to suction load from waves are fastened with more fasteners anchored in wood normal to grain.

The design with the Ice Load Reinforcement Frame (ILoRF) should be implemented as part of the optional yoke for chained mooring line if the Chain Hanger and Adjustment Design (CHAD) should be used.

Figure 11: Yoke assembly for wire mooring line (WHAD)

4.2.2.2 Chain Hanger and Adjustment Design (CHAD)

Optional: An alternative design is also made that accommodate chained mooring line. A chain mooring line requires a more complex system to tension the chain, but the tensioning is on the other hand very controlled and secure and easy to adjust. The CHAD requires more steel, more advanced production processes, and more working hours. Note that the design of the CHAD as shown here does not have the ability to transfer load from sea and ice to the timber caisson.

Figure 12: Chain Hanger and Adjustment Design (CHAD)

4.2.3 Timber fasteners

For the entire design, both for the timber caisson and the anchor plate, Simpson strong-tie type 316 stainless series is used. Dimensions in this document is given in inch, but similar fasteners in SI-units or from other manufacturers may also be used. Type 316 stainless steel for corrosion protection. Simpson strong-tie argue that predrilling is not necessary, but predrilling with $\varnothing 6$ mm would save equipment and machinery wear and is recommended. In any way, if splitting occurs, predrill with 6mm drill bit. A 300-400 mm drill $\varnothing 6$ is suggested to use. For most connections 200 – 300 mm predrilling depth is recommended, but the craftsmen may assess this best. The timber-to-timber fasteners selected here are all partially threaded (3" thread length). Install with 18V high-torque cordless or 1/2" low speed drill.

4.2.3.1 Countersunk flat head cladding screws

Figure 13. The Strong-Drive SDWS TIMBER SS Screw.

The Strong-Drive SDWS TIMBER SS Screw is used for:

- Cladding and bottom planks: SDWS271000SS 0.275 x 10: Shank diameter 0.275". T50 torx bit.
- Decking (for 75 mm decking plank) SDWS27600SS 0.275 x 6: Shank diameter 0.275" with 3" thread length. T50 torx bit.
- See annex D.1

4.2.3.2 Flange head construction screw

Figure 14. The Strong-Drive SDWH TIMBER-HEX SS Screw.

The Strong-Drive SDWH TIMBER-HEX SS Screw. Shank diameter 0.275". 1/2" hex drive head is used for:

- Connection between timber columns: SDWH271000SS 0.275" x 10".
- Timber bracing to columns: SDWH271200SS 0.275" x 12". Predrill to full depth (300 mm).
- Reinforcement members and skid preventer
- See annex D.2

4.2.3.3 A4 coach screw 10x130

- Steel detail to timber: D571-A4 10x130/78 NV17 Hex Coach Screw. Predrilling to full depth (approx. 125 mm) with $\varnothing 6$ mm drill. This is to get better control of the torsion related to fastening of the steel to timber connection.
- See annex D.3

4.2.4 Machine- and stud bolts

Machine bolts, stud bolts and nuts M20 in A4 (316 stainless) quality according to calculations in annex.

4.3 Workshop manufacturing description

In the workshop the vertical plan of the side (i.e. the plane perpendicular to shoreline) of the timber caisson (TC) is marked on the workshop floor with right angles. Mark the level of the mooring line. Also mark the top and bottom of both decking planks and bottom planks. Mark the three braces. Mark the split between lower caisson (LC) and the upper caisson (UC) and note that two of the braces are attached to the UC, and must therefore not be fasten to members of the LC. **Note the important difference between a number written between two brackets e.g. (7) which refers to a part, and a number followed by a dot, e.g. 7., which refers to a step in this manufacturing description.**

1. Step 1., to step 9., are the manufacturing of the sides of the timber caissons: Produce the correct lengths of the column members (2, 3). Note the inclined cut for weather resistance on top column member and on the tie bar. Produce the notch in the rear top column members for the top brace (4T).
2. Lay out all four columns orientated with the inside of the timber caissons upwards. The column is doubled where the UC and LC are tied together. The member tying the columns together is the tie bar (3). See fabrication drawings annex A. The column members are laid directly on the floor, and the tie bars are placed on top of the column members. There are three column members and one tie bar in each column. One tie bar is shifted downwards toward the LC with 200 mm to work as guide during installation. The position if this guiding tie bar should be placed on a column towards the soil side, and not on the side where the anchor load distribution yoke is mounted. Fasten the tie bar to the upper column member with 4 X flange head construction screw and the middle piece with 2 x flange head construction screw. Pre-drill according to own judgement or according to guidance in section 4.2.3.2 Flange head construction screw.
3. For the transition from UC to LC, mark the holes for M20 stud bolt, and temporarily fasten the tie bar to the column member of the LC with 2 x flange head construction screw where the M20 later should be mounted.
4. Store two of the column assemblies and rotate the other two so that the tie bar faces down on the workshop floor. Stabilize and orient with workshop marks.
5. Produce the length and angles of the braces according to the columns. The length and angles on the drawings is approximations as the members used for the column probably deviate from theoretical dimensions.
6. Fit all three braces between the columns and insert fastener between top brace and column using 1 x flange head construction screw.
7. Mount the four upper planks and the extreme lower planks. Also mount the two planks located at the separation point between UC and LC and fasten these. Add two more planks on the LC just below the one positioned at the separation point. The cladding planks are fastened with 2 x Countersunk flat head cladding screws in each end of the plank.
8. Mount the bottom bracing to the last two side planks mounted.
9. Make a mirrored version of the step 4. to 8. using the two other column assemblies produced in 2.
10. Place a few front cladding planks on the workshop floor and place the two prefabricated sides on top of these planks so that the sides have the correct distance and orientation between them, and with the seaside pointing towards the workshop floor. Stabilize the two sides temporarily.
11. Prefabricate the ILoRF in three parts: The central part (6), the upper extension (one or two depending on the decking planks capacity¹) with inclined cut for weather resistance (7), and the lower extension (8). For the central part (6), the drawings indicate bulldogs, but this is not necessary unless machine bolts are used (i.e. bulldogs not used if recommended fasteners for

¹ Make two upward extension members unless otherwise stated. This allows for increased capacity for the decking. Also add two members (beams) between the extension members unless otherwise stated. These two beams increase the capacity of the decking planks from 4.5 to 9 kN point load, and from 22.5 to 90 kN/m² uniformly distributed load.

reinforcements are used). **NB: Fasten the upper extensions permanently. Fasten the downward only temporarily (with one screw).**

12. Place and fasten the two bottom withdrawal reinforcement members (5) to the bottom extension members (8) of the ILoRF. Also, if applicable, temporarily fasten two 75 mm beams on each side of the upward extension members (7).
13. Place the ILoRF atop the cladding planks and in the centre between the sides of the timber caisson and stabilize at the correct position.
14. Mount the extreme rear cladding planks (one at the top and one at the bottom) using the same fasteners as for the side cladding. Also mount the two planks located at the separation point between UC and LC and fasten these.
15. Secure the ILoRF in these four cladding planks.
16. Carefully insert the WHAD (or CHAD) inside the timber caisson skeleton. The 1/3-position brackets on the WHAD should now coincide with the ILoRF. Mount the WHAD (or CHAD) using 4.2.3.3. Now the assembly should look like Figure 15 in a workshop floor projection.

Figure 15: Assembly step 16

17. Now drill holes for stud bolts through column and cladding at 90 degrees on the surface. These holes must be drilled with high level of accuracy. Use $\varnothing 30$ mm drill bit for the final hole.
18. Disassembly the temporarily fastening of the transition part of the tie bar (the two fasteners mounted in step 3., as well as the temporary connection between (6) and (8).
19. Carefully take UC and LC from each other and place both LC and UC with the top facing down on the workshop floor. This shall allow to work on the bottom cladding of the LC, and the UC with be stable on the workshop floor with the guiding leg and tie bars pointing up.
20. With the UC and LC separated, mount the top fastener for the bottom bracing (on the LC) using 1 x flange head construction screw. See Figure 16 (shown with the bottom down and not with the top down as will be the situation in the workshop).

Figure 16: Lower Caisson (LC) side view with skid preventers and bottom bracing

21. Mount seaside cladding on both LC and UC with two screws on each position of underlaying members with grain direction normal to the fastening direction². This means 12 screws per seaside cladding plank when the cladding planks meet double column and central part on ILoRF, and it will mean a minimum of 6 screws per cladding plank where there are only single column members and extension members on the ILoRF. This is to cope with wave slamming suction force.
22. Mount remaining cladding and skid preventer on LC.
23. Mount remaining cladding on UC.
24. Fasten bottom planks and additional fastener on bracing on LC using flange head construction screws. Note that any fasteners entering the column should be inserted at 15 degrees to cut through parallel wood grains.
25. Optionally fasten one decking plank on each side of the UP. Note that the underlaying central beams temporarily fastened in (7) must be dismantled in order to lower dead weight bags into the timber caisson.
26. Make a trial installation of the upper part in the lower part before leaving the workshop.

² No fasteners in end-grain members.

5 Description and manufacturing guide for anchor plate

Sveinung Ørjan Nesheim

5.1 Brief

As for the timber caissons the anchor plate is based on Svea mine members, and designed to be manufactured with simple tools and off-the-shelf fasteners. The anchor plate is stiff and designed to be lifted by front loader or other available lifting machinery. The anchor plate can be transported on an ordinary tipper truck. The anchor plate consumes 12 Svea mine members in addition to approximately 3 m of a mix of 10 mm and 16 mm S355 or stainless steel. The total weight of the anchor plate is 450 kg. Figure 17 shows the drawing of the anchor plate.

Figure 17: Anchor plate.

5.2 Components overview

5.2.1 Timber parts

The numbers 50 to 55 are the timber components. Concern is put into designing the anchor plate with as less machining and residual material as practically possible. Positions 53 and 55 are the braces of the anchor plate.

Position 50 and 51: This is the same component, but they have unique identifier to increase the readability of the drawing. This is members of the Svea mine without any modifications. Position 50 and 51 constitute the outer frame of the anchor plate. 4 ea. of each is used for the anchor plate.

Position 52 and 55: Made from the same timber member. There are used two full Svea members to produce 51 and 55 for one anchor plate. Note that the position 52 used towards the direction of the timber caisson (i.e. the front position 52) is cut in half or otherwise modified to allow the chain or wire to pass. Position 52 is here used to secure that the mooring line remains along the centre line of the anchor plate.

Position 53 and 54: Made from the same timber member.

5.2.2 Steel components

The positions 56 to 60 makes the steel component where the mooring load is introduced. This is referred to as Welded Steel Plate Spreader (WSPS) and is custom made in the workshop. Only approximate dimensions is given for the WSPS, and this construction should be manufactured to fit the timber parts of the anchor plate. The role of the WSPS is to transfer load from the mooring line into the anchor plate. The loading in the WSPS is transferred into the braces of the anchor plate (Positions 53 and 55), and the rear position 52, which again distribute the load into the outer frames of the anchor plate. Whilst there is limited shear capacity transfer possibility between position 53 to the outer frame, there is a huge shear capacity transfer capability between positions 55 and rear position 52, to the outer frame. This is due to the availability of shear transfer area, and the grain direction.

5.2.3 Timber fasteners

Same fasteners as for the timber caisson is used. Please see section 4.2.3. for additional information.

5.2.3.1 Flange head construction screw

Figure 18. Fastener SDWS271000SS 0.275" x 10.

Fastener SDWS271000SS 0.275" x 10" is used for all timber to timber members for the anchor plate. The outer frame is only fastened by the middle layer members. Outer frame is screwed to the middle layer from each side of the outer frames respectively.

To transfer shear load from the steel plate spreader 16 screws are required for each of the two outer frames:

- 2 x (1 screw from positions 53 to position 50)
- 2 x (2 screw from positions 53 to position 51 x 2)
- 2 x (2 screw from positions 55 to position 51 x 2)
- 2 x (1 screw from positions 55 to position 50 x 2)
- 1 x (4 screw from rear positions 52 to position 50)

In addition position 54 is fastened by two fasteners from each outer frame, and each half of front position 52 is fastened to the outer frame with two fasteners.

5.2.3.2 Steel to timber details

Steel plate spreader to timber members: A4 coach screw: D571-A4 10x130/78 NV17 Hex Coach Screw.
Predrilling to full depth (approx. 125 mm) with $\varnothing 6$ mm drill bit.

5.3 Workshop manufacturing description

- 1) Precut parts for the middle layer (soil gripper), i.e. position 52 to position 55 according to drawings. There are two of each of the position 52 to 55 for each anchor plate.
- 2) Centre rear position 52 on a position 50 and fasten with four screws according to drawing annex B, and place the assembly on the workshop floor with the position 52 pointing up.
- 3) Lay out rest of positions 50 and 51 on the workshop floor to create the bottom outer frame. Also add a piece of Svea mine members or other block at the centre of the frame to support position 52 of the middle layer on.
- 4) Place the middle layer members on top of the bottom outer frame, and add 10mm and 16mm distance between the members where the steel plate spreader will run.
- 5) Produce steel parts to bend to positions 59 and 60. 150 mm flat steel is used. Three parts of 360 mm of length is cut to make 2 x position 59, and one position 60.
- 6) 2 x $\varnothing 11$ mm holes are drilled approximately 5 cm in from each side and end. Here the $\varnothing 10$ coach screws will be fastened.
- 7) Bend two of the plates to 52 degrees at the middle (approximately 180 mm from each end) to make positions 50
- 8) Bend the other plate at the required distance to wrap the bent plate around the V-shape formed by the braces of position 53. This is position 60.
- 9) Cut the required lengths of plate to form the tensions bars of the spreader (position 56 and 57).
- 10) Drill a hole for an appropriate shackle at the end of position 57.
- 11) Make two donuts in 10 mm steel plate to form the doubling for the shackle pad eye.
- 12) Weld all parts together and make sure that the lengths of the spreader corresponds to the lengths of the timber braces (position 53 and 55).
- 13) A coffee may be well brewed and enjoyed at this time.
- 14) With fresh eyes check that all welds have been made with proper root penetration and shape.
- 15) If the steel spreader is not made of stainless steel, but in S355, then the steel spreader must be painted with a suitable surface treatment system: Typically, this would be two layers of corrosion resisting two-component metal paint.
- 16) Mount the steel spreader to the various positions with $\varnothing 10$ mm coach hex fasteners.
- 17) Add positions 50 and 51 on top of the assembly. These now constitute the top outer frame.
- 18) Fasten all timber members according to drawing annex B.
- 19) Flip the anchor plate so that what was the top outer frame is now facing down on the workshop floor.
- 20) Add the positions 50 and 51 not previously fastened on top of the assemble to make the remaining outer frame.
- 21) Fasten all remaining timber members according to drawing in annex B.
- 22) Check that all fasteners has been mounted.

6 Installation

Sveinung Ørjan Nesheim

6.1 Brief

The installation process is explained in the following sections. Figure 19 shows the top/plan view of the installed components.

Figure 19: Top view of friction plate / anchor plate tied to the timber caisson assembly with mooring line

6.2 Components overview

In addition to the timber caisson and anchor plate the following components are required:

6.2.1 Wire rope mooring line

Figure 20: Wire rope load flow and suggested method for tensioning

Position 61: Galvanized wire rope $\varnothing 20$ mm 6 x 36 IWRC with standard thimble in one end, and with the other end cold cut, e.g. Certex part code: 101100804270231

Position 62: 8 shackles rated at 17 T WLL e.g. Certex part code: 420101700380

Position 63: 2 ea. 120T Frog legs/Wire rope clamps e.g. Certex part code: 140504000010

Position 64: 1 ea. 4 m and 1 ea. 2.5 m 2 leg slings (with single masterlink) and soft eye in both ends, e.g. based on Certex part code: 101100804270231

Position 65: 1 ea. 20 T open wedge socket OWS B with bolt, e.g. Certex part code: 121501000212

Position 66: 1 ea. 1 m and 1 ea. 1.6 m wire rope slings with soft eye in both ends, e.g. Certex part code: 101100804270231

Position 67: 5 ea. Turnbuckle/rigging screw Gunnebo no. 801 jaw – jaw 17T WLL, e.g. Certex part code: 422101700360

Position 68: 4 ea. Wire rope clamp/grip 17-20 T rating e.g. Certex Part code: 121102000090

6.2.2 Chained mooring line

2 shackles rated at 17 T WLL e.g. Certex part code: 420101700380

6.3 Common preparations

- 1) It is here presupposed that the locations of both timber caissons and anchor plate is given, and:
 - a. The locations is roughly horizontally levelled by an excavator.
 - b. The levelled location for the timber caisson allows an approximately 20 cm layer of gravel for accurate levelling.
 - c. The soil of the rear of the timber caissons (towards the anchor plate) is stable.
 - d. A straight (horizontally levelled) ditch is prepared for the mooring line.
- 2) A layer of gravel is laid out to establish a horizontal and levelled adjustable floor/sole for the timber caisson with a prepared relative horizontal tolerance between corners of ± 2 cm.
- 3) Geotextile bag with gravel/soil is prepared for the lower caisson according to drawings.

6.4 Installation of anchor plate

- 1) The anchor plate is lifted and placed in position according to drawing. The length from the anchor plate to the timber caisson is not given herein, and is assessed from site to site.
- 2) Connect the wire or chain to the anchor plate with shackle and secure the shackle with locking pin.
- 3) Add a sheet of geotextile roughly around the shackle and the connection point of the anchor plate to allow for easier recovery and disassembly.
- 4) Lay out mooring line in a straight line towards the timber caisson. Make sure that the wire rope or chain is not rotated.
- 5) The anchor plate and parts of the mooring line shall now be dug into the soil. The soil around and above the anchor plate shall be compressed to establish immediate soil friction.

6.5 Installation of lower caissons

6.5.1 Drained installation site

- 1) In a drained installation pit/site, the lower caisson can be lifted **without** the dead weight (geotextile bag with soil). Without the dead weight the lower caisson can be lifted by bolts through the holes on each column as indicated on the drawings.
- 2) The lower caisson can also be lifted with the geotextile bag in place. This may ease the stable levelling of the lower caissons. **In this case, lifting straps are routed around the lower caissons.**
- 3) Place the lower caisson on the foundation sole and adjust the position/orientation and the level of the lower caisson. The levelling of the lower caisson is crucial for the ease of further installation of adjacent lower caissons or upper caisson. The relative horizontal tolerance between any two corners of the resting lower caisson should be ± 0.5 cm, i.e. ± 0.15 degrees.
- 4) Unless already done, place the dead weight inside the lower caisson.
- 5) Recheck level and position/orientation
- 6) Install all lower caissons first if more than one caisson is to be installed in the same operation: Repeat step 1 to 5 for adjacent lower caisson.

- 7) Unless already done, add the dead weight and monitor the $\varnothing 30$ mm holes where the columns of lower and upper caissons are mounted together. Measures must be taken so that the holes between adjacent lower caissons is aligned. If required, invest time in adjusting the sole by removing the lower caisson temporarily.
- 8) Add two fasteners to secure the alignment of the holes for the stud bolts as indicated on the drawing (denoted assembly part I on the drawing)
- 9) When all lower caissons are installed and secured with the fasteners from point 8, then continue to the upper caissons.

6.5.2 Tidal water in installation site

- 1) The lower caisson must be installed with the dead weight in place to counteract buoyancy. If more than one timber caisson is to be installed in the operation, it is advantageous to have at least two lower caissons ready to be installed with dead weights and lifting straps.
- 2) If a lifting spreader is available, two and two lower caissons can be installed to make the levelling of the lower caissons easier. If this is the case, then add a few fasteners between the cladding to increase the rigidity of the two lower caissons lifted as one entity. This requires heavy lifting machinery.
- 3) Scheduling the installation of lower caissons to low tide minus a couple of hours as this is required to be able to level the lower caissons.
- 4) Invest time in orient and levelling the lower caissons, and so that the relative horizontal tolerance between any two corners of the same lower caisson should be ± 0.5 cm, i.e. ± 0.15 degrees.
- 5) Unless this is already done, add two fasteners to secure the alignment of the holes for the stud bolts as indicated on the drawing (denoted assembly part I on the drawing)
- 6) When all lower caissons are installed and secured with the fasteners from point 8, then continue to the upper caissons.

6.6 Installation of upper caissons

- 1) In undrained site, scheduling the installation of upper caissons to low tide minus a couple of hours to be able to install fastener denoted Assembly part II on the drawing, as well as the four lower stud bolts. The design is made for these fasteners to be mounted at low tide.
- 2) Lift the upper caisson as indicated on the drawing. The upper caisson is installed without the decking planks. Note that one leg is longer than the rest for ease of installation.
- 3) Fasten 2 x timber screw denoted Assembly part II on the drawing, as well as the four short lower stud bolts towards the free side (where no upper caisson shall be installed).
- 4) Install the next upper caisson and fasten 2 x timber screw denoted Assembly part II on the drawing, as well as the lower four long stud bolts towards the previously installed upper caisson.
- 5) Add the geotextile bag for the upper caisson once all the lower stud bolts is fastened for the upper caisson.
- 6) Install the upper four long stud bolts towards the previously installed upper caisson.
- 7) Continue until all upper caissons is installed. Close with fastening last four lower short stud bolts towards the free end of the timber caisson.
- 8) Mounting of decking planks will be done after connection and tensioning of mooring line.

6.7 Connect and tensioning of mooring line

6.7.1 Wire rope mooring line

- 1) Fill soil and gravel so that the soil at the back of the timber caissons is at the same level as the mooring line ditch. Be sure to monitor the timber caissons and stop filling if any indications of

movement of the timber caissons are seen. This is also an activity best performed during low tide, as this provides most stability for the timber caisson.

- 2) Tie in the mooring wire rope and add two frog legs runners (63) on the rope.
- 3) Attach one turnbuckle (67) directly (or with shackles) to each of the four pad eyes on the WHAD. Add the long sling (64) to the outer turnbuckle pair, and the short sling (64) to the inner turnbuckle pair. Add each of the masterlinks on the slings (64) to the frogs (63) using a shackle (62).
- 4) The tensioning is now done by rigging screws. **Make sure that all the rigging screws are lubricated well.** Start with the short sling and tension the available length of the turnbuckle. Offload the short sling by the long sling and repeat the process. Depending on the turnbuckles and the angle, the tension of the wire may be calculated, but at this point, the tension may be moderate. Moderate tension is reached when further tensioning will not take in much more slack, but rather just build up tension.
- 5) Once the required moderate tensioning is reached, the temporary tensioning through the frog leg runners can now be replaced by the open wedge socket: Route the short sling (66) around the central part of the WHAD. Choose the length of sling that suit the geometry, and route the sling with a half turn around the tube between stoppers that are welded on the tube. Add on end of the sling to the wedge socket and the other to a rigging screw. The other end of the rigging screw will then be connected to the wedge socket.
- 6) With the above system properly setup, make a soft eye with the wire rope end using cable grippers/clamps (68).
- 7) Use the unloaded frog leg and one of the unloaded turnbuckles and add these to the free end of the wire rope and tension the mooring line wire rope that is now running through the wedge socket (65). When the tension proper tension is reached, the wedge in the socket will secure the connection. Check this by unloading the rigging screw connected to the soft eye on the free end of the wire.
- 8) Unload the other frog leg and keep attention to the socket wedge and sling around the WHAD to see that tension is now taken up there.
- 9) With the sling (66) routed in series with the rigging screw, the rigging screw has half the load of the mooring line. Tension the rigging screw to approximately 700 Nm to approach 185 kN. This is a very high torque, and it may be difficult to achieve this in practice. The torque is also rather approximate, and there is a lot of friction in this system, but the calculation indicates these quantities.

6.7.2 Chained mooring line

- 10) Fill soil and gravel so that the soil at the back of the timber caissons is at the same level as the mooring line ditch. Be sure to monitor the timber caissons and stop filling if any indications of movement of the timber caissons are seen. This is also an activity best performed during low tide, as this provides most stability for the timber caisson.
- 11) Tie in the mooring chain and tread the chain between the yoke and the hanger plate on the CHAD. Tension and straighten the chain without any rotation as good as possible and with manual labour.
- 12) Put the traveller plates around the chain and slip the traveller plate assembly on to the stud bolts of the CHAD and put on the nuts on the traveller plate.
- 13) Fasten the traveller plate to the chain link furthest away from the CHAD with the M27 bolt.
- 14) Tension the nuts on the stud bolts so that the chain starts to tension. Keep the tension balanced between the two stud bolts.
- 15) Cover the open gap where the mooring line enters the timber caisson with geotextile or with plates so that too much soil is entering into the timber caissons.
- 16) An iterative process: The final tension is 185kN of the mooring line. For a lubricated stainless steel bolt this correspond to 220 Nm. This tension can also only be achieved if the soil on the back of the timber caisson is filled up and compressed. Therefore, the process with tensioning the mooring

should be balanced with the potential reaction force from the soil at the back of the timber caisson. Monitor any change in movement or inclination of the timber caisson and compensate with back filling and compression if movement or rotation occurs. The goal is to have an iterative process where backfilling and compressions of soil is done in line with tensioning of the mooring line.

- 17) Backfilling and compressions must be completed before 185 kN is reached, so that the 185 kN is reached with tensioning and not as a response of the backfilling or compression of the soil.
- 18) If the traveller plate reaches the end of the stud bolts before the appropriate tensions is reached, the traveller is unloaded until the next chain link is hooked onto the hanger plate. Then the M27 bolt of the traveller plate can be unscrewed, and the traveller plate be moved further up the chain for a new grip.

6.8 Completion

- 1) Check inclination and rotation of the timber caissons
- 2) Check all bolts.
- 3) Secure nuts on the traveller plate for the CHAD with counter nuts. Likewise secure the tensioning of the turnbuckles with locking pins (or as the design of the turnbuckle allow).
- 9) Mount optional beams for increased capacity of decking planks, and decking planks according to drawings. Note tolerances to allow swelling of timber.

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A Fabrication drawing for ClimaRest Timber Caisson

Side view assembly section A-A:
 Plan perpendicular to shore line (cladding parallel to view is shown in transparent to reduce information)

- Notes:
- 1) Marine datum levels as opposed to NN 2000
 - 2) Allow 5% tolerance due to moisture-driven expansion perpendicular to grain
 - 3) Max height of sandbag to ensure that guide leg of upper caisson is not hindered
 - 4) Recommended height of gravel (@2000kg/m³) bag to counteract buoyancy of timber caisson
 - 5) Decking planks marked grey to be installed on-site after internal work in the caissons is done

Section E-E (with hidden reinforcements):
 Design with wired mooring line (WHAD)
 The CHAD is here replaced with yoke with four padeyes for e.g. 801 Gunnebo turnbuckles and wire grab shackles. The yoke is doubled in the center piece to withstand wire stress concentrations

B Fabrication drawing for ClimaRest anchor plate

Parts view scale 1:50 @ A3

Wire rope load flow and suggested method for tensioning

Top view of friction plate / anchor plate tied to the timber caisson assembly with wire

Top view of friction plate / anchor plate tied to the timber caisson assembly with chain

Top view

C Generic stability calculations for timber caisson with environmental loads

Annex G1

Ental kontrollbergrning

3/4-2025

C1-1 Forutsetninger og lastfordeling

Antar

- permanent last og klimaklasse 3 $\Rightarrow k_{mod} = 0,5$
- treverk C18 (p.g.a. alder)
- $\gamma_M = 1,25$

trykk	$f_{c0k} = 18 \text{ MPa}$
Fastheter	bøyn $f_{mk} = 18 \text{ MPa}$
	strekk $f_{k0k} = 10 \text{ MPa}$
	trykk \perp $f_{c90k} = 2,2 \text{ MPa}$
	skjær $f_{vk} = 3,4 \text{ MPa}$
ρ	$\rho = 320 \text{ kg/m}^3$

Lastfordeling:

Antar ingen last via ledningsbord (konservativt)

$F_{mt} = 185 \text{ kN}$ kar. last uten lastfjeler

fordelles på 2 sider

$$F_m = F_{mt} / 2 = 92,5 \text{ kN}$$

$$F_{m0} = \frac{F_m \cdot 7}{(7+4)} = 58,9 \text{ kN}$$

$$F_{mn} = F_m - F_{m0} = 33,6 \text{ kN}$$

$$F_{zn} = F_{mn} = 33,6 \text{ kN}$$

$$F_{z0} = F_{zn} = 33,6 \text{ kN}$$

F_m fordeles på høyde på ca 2,4m
gir jevnt fordelt last på "søyle".

$$q = F_m / 2,4 \text{ m} = 92,5 \text{ kN} / 2,4 \text{ m} = \underline{38,5 \text{ kN/m}}$$

Trykkekraft i skråbjelke:

$$F_o = \sqrt{(58,9^2 + 33,6^2)} = \underline{67,8 \text{ kN}}$$

C1-2 Skråbjelke og søyle

Skråbjelke:

Dim. trykbelast:

$$F_{0y} = F_0 \cdot y_p = 67,8 \text{ kN} \cdot 1,5 = \underline{\underline{102 \text{ kN}}}$$

$$A = b \cdot h = 150 \cdot 200 = \underline{\underline{30\,000 \text{ mm}^2}}$$

$$f_{dk} = \cancel{f_{ok} \cdot \gamma_m}$$

$$f_d = \frac{f_{ok} \cdot \gamma_{red}}{\gamma_m} = \frac{18 \cdot 0,5}{1,25} = \underline{\underline{7,2 \text{ MPa}}}$$

Dim. trykkapasitet:

$$F_d = f_d \cdot A = 7,2 \cdot 30\,000 = \underline{\underline{216 \text{ kN}}}$$

Kontroll: $F_{0y} < F_d$

$$\underline{\underline{102 \text{ kN} < 216 \text{ kN}}}$$

☺/k

Søyle:

Anta en effektiv søyle med $h=200$ og $b=150$:

Moment i søyle (bjelke fritt opplagt):

$$M = q \cdot l^3 / 8 = 38,5 \cdot 2,4^3 / 8 = 27,7 \text{ kNm}$$

$$M_y = M \cdot y_p = 27,7 \cdot 1,5 = \underline{\underline{41,6 \text{ kNm}}}$$

$$W = \frac{b \cdot h^2}{6} = \frac{150 \cdot 200^2}{6} = \underline{\underline{1 \cdot 10^6 \text{ mm}^3}}$$

$$f_d = \frac{f_{mk} \cdot \gamma_{red}}{\gamma_m} = \frac{18 \cdot 0,5}{1,25} = \underline{\underline{7,2 \text{ MPa}}}$$

Dim. momentkapasitet:

$$M_d = f_d \cdot W = 7,2 \text{ N/mm}^2 \cdot 10^6 \text{ mm}^3 = \underline{\underline{7,2 \text{ kNm}}}$$

Kontroll $M_y < M_d$

$$\underline{\underline{41,6 < 7,2}}$$

IKKE ☺/k.!

Kan noe tas opp via kledningsplank?

C1-3 Trykke fra skråbjelke mot søyle:

Dim. trykkraft

$$P_y = F_{mo} \cdot \gamma_p = 58,9 \text{ kN} \cdot 1,5 = \underline{88 \text{ kN}}$$

Trykkeareal:

$$A_{tr} = h' \approx h \cdot \left(\frac{7^2 + 4^2}{7^2} \right) = 200 \cdot 1,33 = 266 \text{ mm}$$

$$A \approx t \cdot h' = 150 \cdot 266 = \underline{39900 \text{ mm}^2}$$

$$f_{cd} = \frac{f_{c90k} \cdot k_{mod}}{\gamma_m} = \frac{2,2 \cdot 0,5}{1,25} = \underline{0,9 \text{ N/mm}^2}$$

Trykkekapasitet (dim.):

$$P_d = f_{cd} \cdot A = 0,9 \text{ N/mm}^2 \cdot 39900 \text{ mm}^2 = \underline{36 \text{ kN}}$$

Kontroll: $P_y < P_d$

$$\underline{88} < \underline{36}$$

Men

Lastfordeling via kledningsplank
og kan regne større lastfordelingsflate,
→ ikke kritiske med deformasjon \approx nok.
Litt sammentrykking har liten
betydning 😊

C1-4 Kledning mot grunn:

Fastholdningskrafta F_{mt} fordeles på anslagsvis 10 kledningsplank

Kraft på hver kledningsplank blir:

$$Q_y = \frac{F_{mt} \cdot \gamma_p}{10} = \frac{185 \text{ kN} \cdot 1,5}{10} = \underline{27,8 \text{ kN}}$$

Kledningsplank regnes som fritt opplagt over spennlengde 1,2 m

$$q_y = \frac{Q_y}{l_{hdc}} = \frac{27,8 \text{ kN}}{2 \text{ m}} = 13,9 \text{ kN/m}$$

Moment (dim.)

$$M_y = q_y l^2 / 8 = 13,9 \cdot 1,2^2 / 8 = \underline{2,5 \text{ kNm}}$$

Kapasitet

$$W = \frac{bh^2}{6} = \frac{200 \cdot 150^2}{6} = \underline{750000 \text{ mm}^3}$$

$$f_d = \frac{f_{mk} \cdot k_{mod}}{\gamma_m} = \frac{18 \cdot 0,5}{1,25} = \underline{7,2 \text{ MPa}}$$

$$M_d = f_d \cdot W = 7,2 \cdot 750000 = \underline{5,4 \text{ kNm}}$$

Kontroll: $M_y < M_d$

$$\underline{2,5 < 5,4} \quad \text{OK}$$

C1-5 Kledning mot sjølast 2 MPa

$$q'_y = 2 \text{ MPa} \cdot \gamma_p = 2 \cdot 1,5 = 3,0 \text{ MPa}$$

Større enn trykkestyrke tre

Last på en kledningsbjelke på 1,2 m lengdespenn

$$Q'_y = q'_y \cdot 1200 \cdot 200 = 3 \cdot 1200 \cdot 200 = \underline{720 \text{ kN}} !$$

$$q_y = Q_y / L = 720 \text{ kN} / 1,2 \text{ m} = \underline{600 \text{ kN/m}}$$

~~My =~~
Moment:

$$M_y = q_y \cdot l^2 / 8 = 600 \cdot 1,2^2 / 8 = 108 \text{ kNm}$$

Momentkap. (som før)

$$M_d = 5,4 \text{ kNm}$$

Kontroll $M_y < M_d$

$$108 < 5$$

IKKE OK !

C1-6 Stabilitet

Virker forankringslinje i krafttyngdepunkt?
Evt. trengs kraft (friksjon) i bunn?

C1-7 Ballast på bunnpånke.

$$m_t = 4725 \text{ kg (fra beregning)}$$

$$F_t = 4725 \cdot 9,81 = \underline{46,4 \text{ kN}}$$

dordelles på 7 pånke, men de 5 mitre tar nok mest

$$F = F_t / 5 = 9,3 \text{ kN pr pånke}$$

$$F_y = F \cdot y_p = 9,3 \cdot 1,5 = \underline{13,9 \text{ kN}} \text{ pr. pånke.}$$

ta hensyn til $k_{mod} = 0,5 \Rightarrow \underline{\underline{\text{Neder. antall skruer.}}}$

Moment i pånke. Bruk $L = 1,8 \text{ m}$

$$p_y = F_y / 1,8 \text{ m} = 13,9 / 1,8 = 7,7 \text{ kN/m}$$

$$M_y = p_y \cdot L^2 / 8 = 7,7 \cdot 1,8^2 / 8 = \underline{3,1 \text{ kNm}}$$

$$\text{Mom-krav} = M_d = 5,4 \text{ kNm}$$

$$M_y < M_d$$

$$\underline{\underline{3,1 < 5,4 \text{ 😊k}}}$$

C1-8 Bolt mot tre ved løft

$$m = 4725 \text{ kg}$$

$$F = 4725 \cdot g = \underline{46,4 \text{ kN}}$$

deles på 4 søyler

$$F_g = \frac{F \cdot \gamma_p}{4} = \frac{46,4 \text{ kN} \cdot 1,5}{4} = \underline{\underline{17,4 \text{ kN}}}$$

$$f_{c0k} = 18 = f_{cd} = \frac{f_{c0k} \cdot k_{mod}}{\gamma_m}$$

($f_{c90k} = 2,2$!)

$$= \frac{18 \cdot 0,5}{1,25} = \underline{\underline{7,2 \text{ MPa}}}$$

$$A = d \cdot t_{\text{bolt spyle}} = 20 \cdot 150 = 3000 \text{ mm}^2$$

Tar opp:

$$F_d = f_{cd} \cdot A = 7,2 \cdot 3000 = \underline{\underline{21,6 \text{ kN}}}$$

$$F_g < F_d$$

$$\underline{\underline{17,4 < 21,6}} \text{ ok}$$

C1-9 SUGKREFTER FRA BØLGER

ref 2024:00725 : 10 kN/m^2

Linjelast : $q = 10 \text{ kN/m}^2 \cdot 0,2 \text{ m} = 5 \text{ kN/m}$

$$\gamma_p = 1,5$$

$$q_g = 1,5 \cdot 5 = 7,5 \text{ kN/m}$$

$$\text{Moment} : M_y = q \cdot l^2 / 8 = 7,5 \cdot 1,7^2 / 8 = \underline{2,7 \text{ kNm}}$$

$$\text{Moment-kapasitet} : M_d = 5,4 \text{ kNm}$$

$$\text{Kontroll } M_y < M_d \quad \underline{2,7 < 5,4} \Rightarrow \underline{\text{ok}}$$

Uttrekk skrue:

$$\text{Last} = F_g = q_g \cdot L_{\text{tot}} = 7,5 \cdot 2,0 = \underline{15 \text{ kN}} \quad \blacktriangledown$$

$$\text{Bruker 4 skrue} \Rightarrow F_{\text{ax}} = 15/4 = 3,8 \text{ kN} = \text{n\u00f8dv. } F_{\text{axd}}$$

N\u00f8dvendig dim. uttrekkkapasitet er $3,8 \text{ kN}$ ved bruk av 4 skrue (2 i hver ende)

M\u00e5 ta hensyn til kn\u00f8d \u00e6gms. og redusert densitet?

D Data sheet for Simpson Strong-Tie® Fastening System

D.1 Strong-Drive SDWS TIMBER SS Screw

Exterior Screws

Strong-Drive® SDWS TIMBER SS Screw

Structural Wood and Engineered Wood Connections Including Docks, Piers and Boardwalks

The SDWS Timber SS screw is a 0.275"-diameter Type 316 stainless-steel fastener suitable for marine and coastal applications where severe-corrosion resistance is a necessity. The SDWS Timber SS screw has a SawTooth® point and flat washer head that make it the ideal choice for use on docks, wharves, piers, boardwalks and ledgers.

Features:

- 0.275" shank diameter for heavy-duty structural applications
- SawTooth point design for fast starts and no predrilling
- Ideal replacement for spikes, lag bolts and lag screws
- No predrilling, no counterboring required for most applications
- Large flat head with nibs can drive flush to surface with reduced splintering
- Deep T50 6-lobe recess for a secure drive (replacement driver bit — BIT50T-2-R1)

For more information regarding driver bits for Simpson Strong-Tie fasteners, see p. 129.

Codes/Standards: IAPMO UES ER-192 (including City of LA Supplement), State of Florida FL13975

For Technical Data and Loads, see C-F-2023TECHSUP *Fastening Systems Technical Guide*, pp. 51–52, 150–152, 158

US Patent: 9,523,383

Type 316 Stainless Steel

Model No.	Dimensions							
	Inches				Millimeters			
	O.D. x Length	Shank Diameter	Thread Length	Head Diameter	O.D. x Length	Shank Diameter	Thread Length	Head Diameter
SDWS27300SS	0.395 x 3	0.275	2	0.650	10 x 76	7.0	51	16.5
SDWS27400SS	0.395 x 4	0.275	3	0.650	10 x 101	7.0	76	16.5
SDWS27500SS	0.395 x 5	0.275	3	0.650	10 x 127	7.0	76	16.5
SDWS27600SS	0.395 x 6	0.275	3	0.650	10 x 152	7.0	76	16.5
SDWS27800SS	0.395 x 8	0.275	3	0.650	10 x 203	7.0	76	16.5
SDWS271000SS	0.395 x 10	0.275	3	0.650	10 x 254	7.0	76	16.5
SDWS271200SS	0.395 x 12	0.275	3	0.650	10 x 305	7.0	76	16.5

See footnotes below.

Multi-Screw Packaging

Individually Flagged		Mini-Bulk		Bucket	
Fasteners Qty.	Model No.	Fasteners per Pack	Model No.	Fasteners per Bucket	Model No.
1	SDWS27300SS-RP1	30	SDWS27300SS-R30	350	SDWS27300SS
1	SDWS27400SS-RP1	30	SDWS27400SS-R30	350	SDWS27400SS
1	SDWS27500SS-RP1	30	SDWS27500SS-R30	300	SDWS27500SS
1	SDWS27600SS-RP1	30	SDWS27600SS-R30	300	SDWS27600SS
1	SDWS27800SS-RP1	30	SDWS27800SS-R30	200	SDWS27800SS
1	SDWS271000SS-RP1	30	SDWS271000SS-R30	—	—
1	SDWS271200SS-RP1	30	SDWS271200SS-R30	—	—

1. O.D. denotes thread outer diameter.

2. Driver bit size: T50.

3. Flagged fasteners per master carton: 3"-4" = 40, 5"-6" = 35, 8"-12" = 25.

Structural and General Fastening

Strong-Drive® SDWS™ TIMBER SS Screw

Structural Wood and Engineered Wood Connections Including Docks, Piers, Boardwalks and Ledgers, Applications Requiring High to Severe Corrosion Resistance

Designed to provide an easy-to-install, low-torque driving, high-strength, severe-corrosion-resistant alternative to through bolting, traditional lags and spikes. The Strong-Drive SDWS Timber SS screw is a premium solution for heavy-duty structural applications. Type 316 stainless steel provides severe corrosion resistance, making it suitable for exterior and preservative-treated wood applications.

Codes/Standards: IAPMO UES ER-192 (including City of LA Supplement), State of Florida FL13975

US Patent: 9,523,383

For more information: see p. 61, C-F-2025 Fastening Systems catalog

SDWS Timber SS – Allowable Shear Loads – Douglas Fir-Larch, Southern Pine Lumber

Fastener Length (in.)	Model No.	Thread Length (in.)	Reference DFL/SP Allowable Shear Loads (lb.)								Reference Withdrawal Design Value, W (lb./in.)	Max. Reference Withdrawal Design Value, W _{max} (lb.)
			Wood Side Member Thickness (in.)									
			1.5	2.5	3	3.5	4.5	6	8	10		
4	SDWS27300SS	2	225	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	222	410
4	SDWS27400SS	3	375	225	—	—	—	—	—	—	204	410
5	SDWS27500SS	3	375	335	310	210	—	—	—	—	204	410
6	SDWS27600SS	3	375	335	335	335	210	—	—	—	204	410
8	SDWS27800SS	3	375	415	485	440	335	275	—	—	204	410
10	SDWS271000SS	3	375	415	485	440	335	275	275	—	204	410
12	SDWS271200SS	3	375	415	485	440	335	275	275	275	204	410

See footnotes below.

SDWS Timber SS – Allowable Shear Loads – Hem-Fir, Spruce-Pine-Fir Lumber

Fastener Length (in.)	Model No.	Thread Length (in.)	Reference HF/SPF Allowable Shear Loads (lb.)								Reference Withdrawal Design Value, W (lb./in.)	Max. Reference Withdrawal Design Value, W _{max} (lb.)
			Wood Side Member Thickness (in.)									
			1.5	2.5	3	3.5	4.5	6	8	10		
3	SDWS27300SS	2	210	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	182	365
4	SDWS27400SS	3	325	180	—	—	—	—	—	—	200	385
5	SDWS27500SS	3	325	285	235	175	—	—	—	—	200	385
6	SDWS27600SS	3	325	285	285	285	175	—	—	—	200	385
8	SDWS27800SS	3	325	350	390	465	280	240	—	—	200	385
10	SDWS271000SS	3	325	350	390	465	280	240	240	—	200	385
12	SDWS271200SS	3	325	350	390	465	280	240	240	240	200	385

- All applications are based on full penetration into the main member. Full penetration is the screw length minus the side member thickness.
- Allowable loads are shown at the wood load duration factor of $C_D = 1.0$. Loads may be increased for load duration per the building code up to a $C_D = 1.6$. Tabulated values must be multiplied by all applicable adjustment factors per the NDS.
- For minimum fastener spacing requirements for both side and main members, see the Spacing Requirements Figure and Table on next page.
- For in-service moisture content greater than 19%, use $C_M = 0.7$.
- Loads are based on installation into the side grain of the wood with the screw axis perpendicular to the face of the member.
- The tabulated reference withdrawal design value, W, is in pounds per inch of the thread penetration into the side grain of the main member.
- The tabulated reference withdrawal design value, W_{max}, is in pounds where the entire thread length must penetrate into the side grain of the main member.
- Embedded thread length is that portion held in the main member, including the screw point.
- Values are based on the lesser of withdrawal from the main member or pull-through of a 1 1/2" side member.

Structural and General Fastening

Strong-Drive® SDWS™ TIMBER SS Screw (cont.)

Wood and Engineered
Wood Fastening

SDWS Timber SS Screw Spacing Requirements

Condition	Direction of Load to Grain	ID	Minimum Distance or Spacing (in.)
Edge Distance	Perpendicular	①	1½
	Parallel	①	1½
End Distance	Perpendicular	②	6
	Parallel	②	6
Spacing Between Fasteners in a Row	Perpendicular	③	4
	Parallel	④	8
Spacing Between Rows of Fasteners	Perpendicular	⑤	4
	Parallel	⑥	4
Spacing Between Staggered Rows	Perpendicular or Parallel	⑦	¾

1. For axial loading only, use the following minimum dimensions: end distance = 4", edge distance = 1½", spacing parallel to grain = 2¾", spacing perpendicular to grain = 2".

D.2 Strong-Drive SDWH TIMBER-HEX SS Screw

Exterior Screws

Strong-Drive® SDWH TIMBER-HEX SS Screw

Structural Wood and Engineered Wood Connections Including Ledgers

Stainless-steel structural fasteners designed for lag-screw replacement. These 0.185" and 0.275" diameter hex-head fasteners require no predrilling, making them easier and faster to install than typical lag screws. It meets 2018 and 2021 IRC® and IBC® code requirements for most common wood framing applications.

Features:

- Type 316 stainless steel for maximum corrosion protection
- No predrilling necessary in most applications
- Driver bit included (replacement driver bit – BITHEXR516-R1 or BITHEXR12-R1)
- Can be used in ledger applications
- Unique "box" thread design with raised-ridge technology significantly reduces driving torque
- Hex-washer head provides large bearing area

For more information regarding driver bits for Simpson Strong-Tie fasteners, see p. 129.

For Technical Data and Loads, see C-F-2023TECHSUP *Fastening Systems Technical Guide*, pp. 64–65, 164–165

Type 316 Stainless Steel

Model No.	Hex Drive (in.)	Dimensions							
		Inches				Millimeters			
		O.D. x Length	Shank Diameter	Thread Length	Head Diameter	O.D. x Length	Shank Diameter	Thread Length	Head Diameter
SDWH19400SS	5/16	0.255 x 4	0.185	2 3/4	0.455	6.5 x 101	4.7	60	11.5
SDWH19450SS	5/16	0.255 x 4.5	0.185	2 3/4	0.455	6.5 x 114	4.7	70	11.5
SDWH19500SS	5/16	0.255 x 5	0.185	2 3/4	0.455	6.5 x 127	4.7	60	11.5
SDWH19600SS	5/16	0.255 x 6	0.185	2 3/4	0.455	6.5 x 152	4.7	60	11.5
SDWH19800SS	5/16	0.255 x 8	0.185	2 3/4	0.455	6.5 x 203	4.7	60	11.5
SDWH27300SS	1/2	0.370 x 3	0.275	3	0.655	9.5 x 76	7.0	76	16.6
SDWH27400SS	1/2	0.370 x 4	0.275	3	0.655	9.5 x 101	7.0	76	16.6
SDWH27500SS	1/2	0.370 x 5	0.275	3	0.655	9.5 x 127	7.0	76	16.6
SDWH27600SS	1/2	0.370 x 6	0.275	3	0.655	9.5 x 152	7.0	76	16.6
SDWH27800SS	1/2	0.370 x 8	0.275	3	0.655	9.5 x 203	7.0	76	16.6
SDWH271000SS	1/2	0.370 x 10	0.275	3	0.655	9.5 x 254	7.0	76	16.6
SDWH271200SS	1/2	0.370 x 12	0.275	3	0.655	9.5 x 305	7.0	76	16.6

See footnotes below.

Multi-Screw Packaging

Individually Flagged		Retail Clamshell		Retail Pack	
Fasteners Qty.	Model No.	Fasteners per Pack	Model No.	Fasteners per Pack	Model No.
—	—	20	SDWH19400SS-R20	—	—
—	—	10	SDWH19450SS-R10	100	SDWH19450SS-R100
—	—	10	SDWH19500SS-R10	100	SDWH19500SS-R100
—	—	10	SDWH19600SS-R10	—	—
—	—	10	SDWH19800SS-R10	50	SDWH19800SS-R50
1	SDWH27300SS-RP1	10	SDWH27300SS-R10	100	SDWH27300SS-R100
1	SDWH27400SS-RP1	10	SDWH27400SS-R10	100	SDWH27400SS-R100
1	SDWH27500SS-RP1	10	SDWH27500SS-R10	50	SDWH27500SS-R50
1	SDWH27600SS-RP1	10	SDWH27600SS-R10	50	SDWH27600SS-R50
1	SDWH27800SS-RP1	10	SDWH27800SS-R10	50	SDWH27800SS-R50
1	SDWH271000SS-RP1	5	SDWH271000SS-R5	25	SDWH271000SS-R25
—	—	5	SDWH271200SS-R5	25	SDWH271200SS-R25

1. O.D. denotes thread outer diameter.
2. 3" flagged fasteners per master carton: 50;
4" flagged fasteners per master carton: 40;
5" flagged fasteners per master carton: 40;
6" flagged fasteners per master carton: 35;
8"–12" flagged fasteners per master carton: 25.

Structural and General Fastening

Strong-Drive® SDWH™ TIMBER-HEX SS Screw

Structural Wood-to-Wood Connections Including Ledgers, Indoor/Outdoor Projects, Applications Requiring High to Severe Corrosion Resistance

Type 316 stainless steel provides severe corrosion resistance, making it suitable for exterior and preservative-treated wood applications.

For more information: see p. 63, C-F-2025 Fastening Systems catalog

SDWH Timber Hex SS Screw — Allowable Shear Loads — Douglas Fir-Larch, Southern Pine, Spruce-Pine-Fir, Hem-Fir

Fastener Length (in.)	Model No.	Thread Length (in.)	Reference Allowable Shear Loads (lb.)		
			Wood Side Member Thickness (in.)		
			1½	3	3½
4	SDWH19400SS	2.40	177	—	—
4½	SDWH19450SS	2.75	177	177	—
5	SDWH19500SS	2.40	177	177	177
6	SDWH19600SS	2.40	177	177	177
8	SDWH19800SS	2.40	177	177	177
4	SDWH27400SS	3.00	235	—	—
5	SDWH27500SS	3.00	235	235	235
6	SDWH27600SS	3.00	235	235	235
8	SDWH27800SS	3.00	235	235	235
10	SDWH271000SS	3.00	235	235	235
12	SDWH271200SS	3.00	235	235	235

- All applications are based on full penetration into the main member. Full penetration is the screw length minus the side member thickness.
- Allowable loads are shown at the load duration factor of $C_D = 1.0$. Loads may be increased for load duration per the building code up to a $C_D = 1.6$. Tabulated values must be multiplied by all applicable adjustment factors per the NDS.
- Table values based on testing in SPF lumber.
- Design values include NDS wet service factor; no adjustment required for in-service moisture content greater than 19%.
- Allowable loads are perpendicular or parallel to grain.
- Installs best with 18V high-torque cordless or ½" low speed drill. If splitting occurs predrill with ⅝" drill bit for SDWH19 screws and ⅜" drill bit for SDWH27 screws.
- Allowable withdrawal load for the SDWH19 screw for DFL/SP is 155 lb./in. and for SPF/HF is 108 lb./in. Allowable load is based on inches of thread penetration into the main member.
- Allowable withdrawal load for the SDWH27 screw for DFL/SP is 260 lb./in. and for SPF/HF is 160 lb./in. Allowable load is based on inches of thread penetration into the main member.
- For LRFD values, the reference connection design values shall be adjusted in accordance with NDS-24, section 11.3.

Strong-Drive® SDWH™ TIMBER-HEX SS Screw (cont.)

SDWH Timber-Hex SS Screw Spacing Requirements

Condition	Direction of Load to Grain	ID	Minimum Distance or Spacing (in.)
Edge Distance	Perpendicular	①	1 7/16
	Parallel	①	1 7/16
End Distance	Perpendicular	②	3
	Parallel	②	3
Spacing Between Fasteners in a Row	Perpendicular	③	3
	Parallel	④	3
Spacing Between Rows of Fasteners	Perpendicular	⑤	3
	Parallel	⑥	3
Spacing Between Staggered Rows	Perpendicular or Parallel	⑦	1 1/2

1. For SDWH19 screws subject to axial loading only, use the following minimum dimensions: end distance: = 2 3/8", edge distance = 1", spacing parallel to grain = 1 5/8", spacing perpendicular to grain = 1".
2. For SDWH27 screws subject to axial loading only, use the following minimum dimensions: end distance = 3 1/4", edge distance = 1 1/8", spacing parallel to grain = 2 3/8", spacing perpendicular to grain = 1 5/8".

D.3 A4 coach screw 10x130

FRANSK TRÄSKRUV D571 A4

Arvid Nilsson deklarerar:

Fransk träskruv D571 A4 med sexkanthuvud. Lämplig för montage i utsatta miljöer, där krav på hög hållfasthet ställs. Exempelvis linträkonstruktioner, beslag och plintjärn. Även för montage med nylonplugg i betong och mursten.

Dessa produkter uppfyller kraven i bilaga ZA i EN 14592:2008+A1:2012.

Är i överensstämmelse med byggproduktdirektivet 89/106/EEC samt 93/68/EEC. De tekniska specifikationerna produkten överensstämmer med är:

Harmoniserad standard

Produkt i enlighet med EN 14592:2008 "Timber Structures – Doweltype fasteners – Requirements".

Typprovningens certifikat

E-30-20802-13, E-30-20695-13, E-30-20805-13, E-30-20807-13, E-30-20809-13, E-30-20811-13, E30-20944-13

Korrosionsbeständighet

Klimatklass 3

Godkännande institut för typprovning

STROJIRENSKY ZKUSEBNI USTAV s.p. Hudcova 56b 621 00 BRNO Czech Republic

Framställningsprocessen uppfyller kraven till FPC system som beskrivs i EN 14592:2008+A1:2012 paragraf 7.3.

Varugrupp: 765

Gäller följande mått:

Diameter	Längd
5,0 mm	25-70 mm
6,0 mm	25-130 mm
7,0 mm	40-180 mm
8,0 mm	35-200 mm
10,0 mm	40-200 mm
12,0 mm	50-200 mm
16,0 mm	70-200 mm

Nominell diameter d	Utdragshållfasthet f ax,k (1)	Utdragshållfasthet f ax,k (2)	Genomdragningshållfasthet f head,k	Flytmoment My,k (3)	Flytmoment My,k (4)	Dragbärförmåga f tens,k	Indrivningsmoment
[mm]	[N/mm ²]	[N/mm ²]	[N/mm ²]	[Nmm]	[Nmm]	[kN]	F _{tor,k} /R _{tor,k} ≥ 1
5,0	16,14 (450 kg/m ³)	12,60 (450 kg/m ³)	24,35 (450 kg/m ³)	7 741	-	9,58	1,90 (450 kg/m ³)
6,0	15,55 (450 kg/m ³)	12,07 (450 kg/m ³)	24,17 (450 kg/m ³)	15 885	22 913	14,92	2,04 (450 kg/m ³)
7,0	13,50 (450 kg/m ³)	8,88 (450 kg/m ³)	23,49 (450 kg/m ³)	27 409	41 004	20,48	1,78 (450 kg/m ³)
8,0	13,28 (450 kg/m ³)	9,47 (450 kg/m ³)	22,81 (450 kg/m ³)	38 574	69 860	27,27	1,93 (450 kg/m ³)
10,0	10,91 (450 kg/m ³)	7,61 (450 kg/m ³)	22,55 (450 kg/m ³)	83 343	106 985	40,47	1,62 (450 kg/m ³)
12,0	12,16 (450 kg/m ³)	9,31 (450 kg/m ³)	22,27 (450 kg/m ³)	124 481	180 135	64,21	1,69 (450 kg/m ³)
16,0	12,47 (450 kg/m ³)	9,88 (450 kg/m ³)	23,43 (450 kg/m ³)	248 936	286 643	112,71	1,79 (450 kg/m ³)

(1) Loading across the fibre

(2) Loading along the fibre

(3) Thread part

(4) Smooth part

Denna deklARATION gäller fram tills produkt, råmaterial eller produktionsprocess förändras så markant att de karaktäristiska egenskapernas värden inte överensstämmer längre.

Kungälv 2013-06-28

Anders Malmqvist
Commodity Manager

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